

The Aporetic Method of Aristotle's *Metaphysics* B in Damascius' *De Principiis*: A Case Study of the First *aporia*

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Introduction

The last scholar of the Platonist Academy of Athens, Damascius (462–post-532 AD), has experienced a revival of interest in recent years concerning his radical departure from much of the previous Neoplatonist tradition, particularly in his positing not the One, but rather the Ineffable, as the first principle of all things. In addition, there has been recent interest in Damascius' aporetic and argumentative strategies, particularly with the first aporetic puzzle (hereafter *aporia*) presented in his work, the *De Principiis* (full title, "Aporetic Problems and Solutions Concerning the First Principles", ἀπορίαι καὶ λύσεις περὶ τῶν πρώτων ἀρχῶν). So far contemporary commentators have focused on Damascius' unique use of aporetic argumentation, or particularly his borrowing of Skeptical argumentative strategies from Sextus Empiricus, emphasizing the subjective angle in which much of the *aporiai* are aimed.

Much work still remains to be carried out on Damascius' unique style of argumentation, especially in the way he employs *aporiai* throughout his works—not just in the *De Principiis*, but also the commentaries and other treatises. For the moment, I wish to look at a thus far little-appreciated aspect of Damascius' *aporiai* in the *De Principiis*, especially with regard to the first *aporia*: the reception and use of Aristotle's aporetic and dialectical strategy, especially from *Metaphysics* Beta. Though Damascius certainly has his own style of argumentation, as well as decidedly different principles compared to Aristotle, Damascius borrows much from Aristotle's understanding of dialectic and its employment in aporetic arguments. Although Damascius certainly means to use his arguments as a means of purifying and clarifying human reason and its limits, it is *also* clear that, like Aristotle in the *Metaphysics*, he uses dialectical and aporetic argumentation to be able to determine and clarify the nature and number of the first principles responsible for all things (τὰ πάντα). In this respect, this paper would be pushing back against the tendency to read Aristotle and Damascius' aporetic strategies in two, diametrically opposed ways: the former in a more "zetetic" manner, where the *aporiai* are construed as merely programmatic and perfunctory for the project of metaphysics; and the latter in a "critical" or "experiential" way, with the *aporiai* meant to induce a subjective state in the soul of the thinker, without clarifying the relation of this state to the discussion of the principles of beings later in the *De Principiis*. My reading aims to show a closer parallel between the two than has been set forth: both Aristotle and Damascius see a critical, aporetic frame of mind as essential to the project of metaphysics, while for both, the aporetic method is aimed at orienting the

inquirer in the right direction toward the principle (or principles) of all things.¹ While respecting the critical difference in the kind of the principle sought (and hence, the nature of the *aporiai* raised), I claim that there is a parallel between Aristotle and Damascius in their framing of *aporiai* as central for the project of metaphysics—and that it has as its end a solution to demarcate principles, even when, in the case of Damascius, the principle “demarcated” is at once inherently capable of being demarcated, as the Ineffable.

In the first section of this paper I will briefly discuss the *De Principiis*' structure and context in the genre of other aporetic treatises, which broadly fit the pattern of *aporiai* as the starting point of the inquiry into principles, as in Aristotle's *Metaphysics* B. In the second section, I will discuss the methodological preface of *Metaphysics* B.1, where Aristotle argues for the need to raise *aporiai* in searching for principles. Aristotle's methodological argument concerning the *aporiai*, and their link to dialectic, reveal how the method is conducive for the inquiry into first principles. That this is also in the background for Damascius is made manifest and argued in the third section, where I analyze the first *aporia* in the *De Principiis* in parallel with the first *aporia* in *Metaphysics* B (sect. 3.1). I look at the *De Principiis*' first *aporia* as a case study of Damascius' similar aim to Aristotle's methodological approach to the *aporiai* in *Metaphysics* B (sect. 3.2), which is particularly exemplified in *Metaphysics* B's first *aporia*. At the end of the third section (3.3), I discuss the dialectical premises, especially “reputable” opinions (*endoxa*), used in the *aporiai* and in Aristotle and Damascius' dialectical engagement with their respective predecessors, where the premises employed lend themselves to contrary, opposed positions on the objects of inquiry in themselves. In this respect, though well-recognized in Damascius' framework, even Aristotle also recognizes the feature of contrariety and opposition as characteristic in the different perceptions and positions on features of reality: hence, *aporiai* serve as the means of clarifying our concepts in relating to reality and attaining determinate understanding while reconciling with the indeterminacy of one's initial perception of beings.

1. Damascius' *De Principiis* in Context as an Aporetic Treatise

In order to look at Aristotle's influence in Damascius' *aporiai* in the *De Principiis*, it is worth first reflecting on the nature of the work as a whole, especially in its format of “problems and resolutions” (*ἀπορίαι καὶ λύσεις*). Unlike his commentaries on the *Phaedo* and *Parmenides Commentaries*, where problems and topics are discussed in relation to specific passages from the dialogues, Damascius' *De Principiis* forms a self-standing collection of questions, *aporiai*, and arguments on the different levels of metaphysical principles, both treated

¹ In this, I am *not* denying certain, important differences that remain: for instance, that Damascius does, rather, use *aporiai* more centrally than Aristotle does (or seems to) in the *Metaphysics*, and that hence there are additional factors involved in his aporetic method than in Aristotle. What I wish to stress is that this is ultimately a difference in degree, not in kind, as I go on to show.

in themselves and different positions posited on them by various philosophical predecessors.² In sum, the *De Principiis* treats of the first principle as Ineffable (τὸ ἄρρητον, τὸ ἀπόρρητον) (*DP* I, 1–61), the One (*DP* I, 62–131), the first intelligible triad (*DP* II, 40–214), procession in the domain of the intelligible triad and Intellect (*DP* III, 1–107), and participation (*DP* III, 168–174).³ In addition, the treatise dialectically discusses at length prior Neoplatonist positions on the number and nature of first principles and the intelligible triad (*DP* II, 1–39), and also previous theological traditions, like the *Chaldaean Oracles* and the Egyptians, in relating their principles with his enunciated framework (*DP* III, 108–167).⁴

Throughout the work in each topic discussed, Damascius typically presents a series of dialectical questions within which he raises difficulties about aspects of the ontological principles in question—oftentimes also raising difficulties about the way we refer to the principles, either in concepts or language. The way that Damascius discusses the questions can be dense, if obscure, often without a clear structure or order in the way the questions are raised. One example of this is Damascius’ arguments for the ineffable nature of the first principle in *DP* I, 4–26, in which the principle’s transcendence necessitates such attributes as being entirely unknowable (ἄγνωστον),⁵ not an object of opinion (ἀδόξαστον),⁶ nothing (οὐδέν),⁷ beyond any notion of unity,⁸ and even implying an overturning, or self-contradiction, in speech (περιτροπή).⁹ By this point one might think there is nothing more to be said about the Ineffable, yet then afterward, in *DP* I, 27–62, Damascius raises three dialectical demonstrations, or “ascents” (ἀναβάσεις), to the first principle, showing in each case how the true first principle must be something beyond the One: in each case, the ascent “fails” in adequately grasping the final principle. One could ask why Damascius seeks to restart the dialectical consideration on the Ineffable again—and why Damascius considers *three* “ascents”, let alone positing them in addition to the earlier discussion in *DP* I, 4–26. One can find various other cases like this, where Damascius initially raises a question and then settles on an answer, only to come back to the same issue again in another argumentative context. Still, Damascius seems

² In the manuscript tradition, the *De Principiis* was historically grouped with Damascius’ *Parmenides Commentary*, which starts at the *Parmenides*’ second hypothesis (Plato, *Parm.* 142b–155e), where the work was attributed as part of the *Commentary*’s now-lost analysis of the *Parmenides*’ first hypothesis (Plato, *Parm.* 137c–142a). As Westerink-Combès point out in their preface to *De Principiis* I (lvi–lvii; cf. Van Riel (2010) 669–670), not only is the work different in format and philologically from the *Parmenides Commentary*, but it also works through multiple previous Neoplatonist frameworks—like Porphyry’s, Iamblichus’, and Proclus’—in contrast to the *Commentary* which primarily follows the structure of Proclus’ *Parmenides Commentary*, often responding to it.

³ Unfortunately the final treatise on participation breaks off in the middle of Damascius’ defense of participation (*DP* III, 171–175), after Damascius offers a definition of participation (*DP* III, 168–169) and arguments critiquing participation (*DP* III, 169–171). It is uncertain whether and how far Damascius intended the *De Principiis* to go (e.g. into Intellect? Or Soul? etc.). Van Riel (2010) 670 claims that the *De Principiis* “does not go far beyond a discussion of the first hypothesis”, which is certainly true in *DP* I and part of II, but certainly not true for most of II and III.

⁴ This is of course only a very general overview, and not meant to go into extensive detail on the parts. Here I also use “dialectal” in the Aristotelian sense, i.e. tracing an argument to its conclusion from chosen premises: see below n. 53.

⁵ Damascius, *DP* I, 13,17–23.

⁶ Damascius, *DP* I, 14,20–16,17, esp. 15,22–16,4.

⁷ Damascius, *DP* I, 7,20–8,5.

⁸ E.g. Damascius, *DP* I, 3,21–4,12; 11,6–16.

⁹ Damascius, *DP* I, 20,5–22,19 (esp. 22,15–19), 26,3–8.

to present questions as these not solely as a gymnastics in logical (or even rhetorical) exercise, but as careful, yet critical, attempts to ascertain the nature of the principles in question—especially where the method of questioning and raising difficulties brings out different aspects of the principles, both in themselves and in the way they manifest within the soul's reflection from its level of reality.¹⁰

This style of the *De Principiis* roughly fits the general description of treatises in the format of ἀπορίαι καὶ λύσεις, “problems and solutions”, seen in works like Alexander of Aprosias’ *Quaestiones*¹¹ and *Ethical Problems*, which are collections of aporetic questions raised, with solutions presented within each set question. Alexander’s treatises are a particularly relevant parallel for Damascius’ text, insofar as they clarify issues that are either incipient in Aristotle’s texts or that come from outside the texts—for instance from the Stoics—and attempt to give a unified reading of Aristotle’s position across different texts, beyond Aristotle’s own words.¹² In this respect, Alexander’s use of the dialectical question format, especially his use of *aporiai*, is striking inasmuch as he attempts to develop a unified Aristotelian position from a series of difficulties raised dialectically, rather than based on a demonstrative argument or series of propositions.¹³ In a similar way, Damascius attempts this same approach in the *De Principiis*, albeit in terms of developing a unified position from previous Platonists—not just from “Plato” in himself. Throughout the treatise Damascius implicitly and explicitly refers back to his prior Neoplatonist predecessors and their positions in his own formulation of what constitutes a more correct, unified Platonist framework. Damascius’ intention is thus similar to Alexander in drawing together distinct, various positions of previous Neoplatonists, while also drawing on other figures and texts outside the formal Platonist school, like the *Chaldaean Oracles* as well as Aristotle.¹⁴ One could thus describe the *De Principiis* as a kind of commentary on commentaries: like Alexander, in drawing from and critiquing previous Aristotelians, Stoics, and other philosophers, Damascius’ discussion is not so much a commentary on Plato in himself, but rather on the positions that have accrued among past Platonist commentaries on Plato, ultimately in the quest to re-assess the principles of Being.

In the background to the genre of “problems and resolutions” treatises, like Alexander’s and Damascius’ works, stands Aristotle’s *Metaphysics* B. On the one hand, B differs greatly from the former works insofar as it only lists the aporetic questions and gives a series of opposing arguments for each question—whereas

¹⁰ See below, p. 29 ff. where I partially agree with commentators like Metry-Tresson (2012) who claim the *aporiai* are effectively pedagogical logical exercises for the soul, while I also claim there is more of an objective corollary than has been estimated by those like her.

¹¹ In its longer title form, *School-Discussion Difficulties and Solutions on Nature* (φυσικαὶ σχολικαὶ ἀπορίαι καὶ λύσεις).

¹² As Madigan (1987) has noted for the *Ethical Problems*, Alexander brings together different Aristotelian theses spelled out in other works in addressing specific issues: for instance, Aristotle’s notion of physical mixture is used to illustrate one answer to the problem of whether virtue is a totality or a genus (cf. Alexander, *Problemata* 28); the order of the universe is used to argue that activity is prior, and thus superior, to pleasure (cf. Alexander, *Problemata* 23, 144,17 ff.); and so on. See Sharples’ commentary in Alexander’s *Ethical Problems* (1990) 5; cf. Sharples (1987) 1179–1180.

¹³ As, for instance, what one sees in Proclus’ *Elements of Theology*—or closer to home, in Alexander’s terrain, his *De Fato* or *De Providentia* as treatises. On Alexander’s views of *aporia* in relation to the philosophical method in Aristotle, see Kupreeva (2018).

¹⁴ Granting, of course, that they were part of the standard curriculum for Platonists in the Athenian Academy: on this see Griffin (2016).

Alexander's and Damascius' works generally also include their own responses to the *aporiai* in the same work. Yet like the “problems and resolutions” works, B is similar in collecting a series of critical arguments, if somewhat disparate, which become the starting points for the rest of Aristotle's inquiry in the *Metaphysics*—and ultimately for his final position on a number of topics related to first philosophy.¹⁵

Metaphysics B is effectively composed of 15 *aporiai*, while they have been typically grouped into two sets: the “methodological” *aporiai* 1–4 (*Metaphysics* B.1–2), on the scope and subject-matter of the science of wisdom (σοφία); and the remaining *aporiai* 5–15 (*Metaphysics* B.2–6) which address a varying, disparate set of substantive metaphysical problems on the principles of things.¹⁶ Though the latter set are concerned with individual, relatively self-contained issues in the *Metaphysics*, the former, “methodological” *aporiai* relate to the subject matter of the *Metaphysics* as a whole. The subject of these first *aporiai* hearkens back to the first Book A, where Aristotle establishes the theme of the *Metaphysics* as concerned with wisdom (σοφία) as the science, or scientific knowledge (ἐπιστήμη), of causes and principles¹⁷—more specifically, primary principles and causes connected with “the good or that-for-the-sake-of-which” (τὰγαθὸν καὶ τὸ οὐ ἔνεκα ἔν) over all things.¹⁸ As Aristotle recognizes at the end of Book A, all previous predecessors touched on this science, yet in vague, inarticulate ways:¹⁹ this requires going back over the topics which were previously, yet inarticulately, discussed and raising *aporiai* (ἀπορήσειεν) directly on those topics—effectively announcing his attention for Book B.²⁰ As various commentators have highlighted,²¹ it is this anticipation that would make one read Aristotle's intention for going through the *aporiai* in *Metaphysics* B as directly connected with the inquiry he first sets out in Book A, especially from the final chapter of A.10. This will prove important in reading the *aporiai* in Book B as essential for Aristotle's general project in the *Metaphysics*.

With the context of the inquiry from Book A in mind, the first four *aporiai* directly address the central issue of the primary causes in the following ways:

¹⁵ In this respect I follow commentators like Laks (2009) (esp. 40), Politis (2003), Menn (Forthcoming), and others in rejecting the claim of Aubenque (1961) (esp. 17) and (2003) (esp. 10 ff.) that the *aporiai* in the *Metaphysics* do not lead to a determinate resolution, but are continually open-ended. However, as I discuss in the next section, Aubenque's conception of certain of the *aporiai* raised by Aristotle as open-ended, and not implying a simple solution that jettisons the critical state of mind imposed by the *aporia*, is amenable to the aporetic approach I later discuss with Damascius.

¹⁶ On the division and its history, see Madigan's commentary in Aristotle (1999) xiii–xvi; and Crubellier and Laks (2009) 1–2.

¹⁷ Aristotle, *Met.* A.1, 981b25–982a3.

¹⁸ Aristotle, *Met.* A.2, 982b4–10.

¹⁹ Aristotle, *Met.* A.10, 993b11–24.

²⁰ Aristotle, *Met.* A.10, 993b24–27. More pertinent for the “methodological” *aporiai*, Aristotle additionally argues at the end of Book α (α.3, 995a17–20) that, since the inquiry into wisdom concerns all things—including non-material objects, like mathematical or immaterial entities—it cannot be like the inquiry into the natural sciences which involve matter: one must subsequently ask whether there is then one, or more than one, science on the causes and principles. This latter line directly points to the first *aporia* in *Met.* B.1. Although note the important caveat of Laks (2009) 129: “...but even if chapter 2 of Book α may be considered to be answering an *aporia* concerning the number of causes (is it finite or infinite?), the book as a whole can hardly be said to engage in *aporiai* in a way which would match the announcement in A.10.”

²¹ E.g. Politis (2003) 147 ff., Laks (2009) 28–30, and Buddensiek (2018) 138–139.

1. Does it belong to one or several sciences to study the primary causes?²²
2. Does wisdom study only principles of substances, or principles of demonstration as well?²³
3. If wisdom pertains to substance, is there a unique science for all the kinds of substance?²⁴
4. Does wisdom study only substance, or also their essential properties?²⁵

Among the four (if not all the *aporiai*), the first *aporia* is the broadest and appears to correspond most directly with *Metaphysics A*'s definition of wisdom as concerned with the “primary causes and principles” connected to the good. For this reason, as we will see, this will be an apt *aporia* to compare with the first *aporia* in Damascius' *De Principiis*, which is also the broadest among the *aporiai* raised at the beginning of the *De Principiis*, and also sets the agenda for the ensuing inquiry on principles.

2. Aristotle's Methodology for *aporiai* in *Metaphysics B.1*

Yet before we can look at the first *aporia* in Book B, we should review Aristotle's aporetic methodology in the preface of B.1, which will be important to understand the context of the ensuing *aporia*—including the first *aporia*—and eventually see on what grounds to compare Aristotle's approach with Damascius in the *De Principiis*. Already one general question that stands out is how the preface is to be read in relation to the ensuing *aporiai*—i.e. to what degree the method set out in B.1's preface is applied to the ensuing *aporiai* in the rest of B, and to whatever degree (or not) they are answered in the rest of the *Metaphysics*.²⁶ The impression one may get is that, with Aristotle's announcement of his intention in the beginning of B, the *aporiai* play a merely pedagogical role for perfunctorily performing the study of metaphysics—i.e. the *aporiai* are merely procedural for doing metaphysics.²⁷ Yet as we will see, this is far from the case.²⁸

But first, let us see how Aristotle announces his intention, and how he understands the nature of *aporia* in this context:

It is necessary, with a view to the scientific knowledge (*ἐπιστήμην*) which we are looking for, first to go over topics about which we should first experience *aporiai* (*ἀπορήσαι*).²⁹ These include both

²² Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996a18–b26.

²³ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996b26–997a15.

²⁴ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 997a15–25.

²⁵ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 997a25–34.

²⁶ Here I agree with Laks (2009) 45–46, that “[...] the initial remarks of B should not be taken as having a methodological scope. They define, rather, what the relation of an impasse to its solution should in principle be. Again, what this relation really is cannot be decided except on the basis of a complete interpretation, not only of the remainder of Book B, but of the *Metaphysics* as a whole.”

²⁷ As Alexander of Aphrodisias seems to suggest in the beginning of his commentary, *In Met.* 172,14–21, and later at 236,26–29; cf. Laks (2009) 40.

²⁸ Concurring with those like Aubenque (1961).

²⁹ Here I follow Laks (2009)'s choice to translate *ἀπορέω* in this context as “experience the impasse” (where he translates *ἀπορία* as “impasse”: see discussion in 25–26), reflecting the original sense of the term, to be in a state of blockage or impasse, in distinction to the sense of *διαπορέω* as “going through” or “discussing” the *aporia* or things causing *aporia* (discussed more below). In turn, I opt to stick with the transliteration, *aporia/aporiai*.

topics about which certain people have supposed divergent things, as well as any separate from these that may have been overlooked.

Now for those wishing to advance freely (εὐπορήσαι) it is useful to develop the *aporiai* well (τὸ διαπορήσαι καλῶς).³⁰ For the subsequent free advance (ἢ ὕστερον εὐπορία) is a release from what were earlier matters of *aporia*, and it is not possible to unbind a bond of which you are unaware. But an *aporia* in thinking (διανοίας) shows this in the subject matter (περὶ τοῦ πράγματος). For insofar as thought is in *aporia* (ἀπορεῖ), it is in a state similar to people who are in bonds, since in both cases it is impossible to move forward. (995a24–33; trans. Reeve, modified)³¹

ἀνάγκη πρὸς τὴν ἐπιζητούμενην ἐπιστήμην ἐπελθεῖν ἡμᾶς πρῶτον περὶ ὧν ἀπορήσαι δεῖ πρῶτον· ταῦτα δ' ἐστὶν ὅσα τε περὶ αὐτῶν ἄλλως ὑπειλήφασί τινες, καὶν εἴ τι χωρὶς τούτων τυγχάνει παρεωραμένον.

ἔστι δὲ τοῖς εὐπορήσαι βουλομένοις προὔργου τὸ διαπορήσαι καλῶς· ἢ γὰρ ὕστερον εὐπορία λύσις τῶν πρότερον ἀπορουμένων ἐστὶ, λύειν δ' οὐκ ἔστιν ἀγνοοῦντας τὸν δεσμόν, ἀλλ' ἢ τῆς διανοίας ἀπορία δηλοῖ τοῦτο περὶ τοῦ πράγματος· ἢ γὰρ ἀπορεῖ, αὐτῇ παραπλήσιον πέπονθε τοῖς δεδεμένοις· ἀδύνατον γὰρ ἀμφοτέρως προελθεῖν εἰς τὸ πρόσθεν.

Aristotle connects the inquiry into scientific knowledge (ἐπιστήμη) with the state of freely advancing, or, in other words, being free of *aporia* (εὐπορία): to be able to carry on a study of principles in themselves, as implied by ἐπιστήμη, one must be clear of the difficulties which block one's path to attaining those principles.³² One can see this implied from the original definition of the term, ἀπορία, meaning a physical blockage in a pathway or flow:³³ this sense of the term then refers to the thing itself causing the blockage. Equally notable is Aristotle's use of the term, δεσμόν, i.e. “bond” or “chain” which holds someone back, in connection with the term ἀπορία: the imagery behind the term, together with Aristotle's later language, suggests the analogy of the chains which fetter a prisoner, unable to walk out and be free.³⁴ In turn, this suggests a noteworthy modification of the original sense of ἀπορία by Aristotle, when he connects the term with the people who are tied up (δεδεμένοις), not just the object causing the blockage or the chain tying people (or prisoners) up—which is indicative of the state of *aporia*. Between the imagery Aristotle uses of the bond (δέσμον), the physical sense of “blockage” in a flow with ἀπορία, and the people or prisoners stuck in the bond, one can see that Aristotle is connecting the state of

³⁰ Here roughly concurring with Laks' version of διαπορήσαι, “to develop the impasses well”.

³¹ Translations my own unless otherwise noted (as here).

³² This would go with a reading of the necessity for *aporiai* for the project of metaphysics, or ἐπιστήμη of the first principles of beings: for this reading, among others, see Halper (2009) 213–214, Buddensiek (2018) 147–153, and Politis (2003).

³³ In the Liddell–Scott–Jones lexicon entry for the term, the first sub-entry, for places, is “difficulty of passing”; of things, “difficulty, straits”; of persons, “difficulty of dealing with [or] getting at”; and in dialectic, “question for discussion, difficulty, puzzle”. See also the detailed discussion of the different terms used for ἀπορία, διαπορεῖν, etc. in the context of *Met. B* in Madigan's commentary in Aristotle (1999) xix–xxii.

³⁴ Laks (2009) 42–43 suggests that Aristotle likely has in mind specifically the imagery of prisoners deprived of their freedom of movement to describe the position of thought and what causes its impasse: “It simply seems better to assume that what Aristotle is claiming here is that an intellectual blockage displays the same structure as a physical blockage (not the bond, that is, but rather the relationship between knowledge of and release from the bond), but that it does so at the level of *to pragma*, i.e. of how things are in reality.”

aporia to both the object causing that state—and the subject who finds him- or herself in the state of being stuck and at an impasse.

Aristotle's claim of the impossibility to unbind “a bond of which you are unaware” directly recalls Plato's *Meno* 80a–d, where Meno and Socrates discuss the state of *aporia* they find themselves in when realizing neither has knowledge of virtue and what it is. In responding to Socrates' statement that neither he nor Meno know what virtue is, Meno says: “How will you aim to search for something you do not know at all? If you should meet with it, how will you know that this is the thing that you did not know?”³⁵ As various commentators recognize well, Aristotle appears to draw on this background implicitly in our passage, and in this he seems to be responding to, and building on, Plato's aporetic framework. In the *Posterior Analytics*, Aristotle explicitly cites Plato's dialogue when he argues that, in order to avoid the paradox of the *Meno's aporia*, one must admit that we already know something about the object of inquiry.³⁶ Though reference or use of *aporia* is absent in the *Analytics*, it is likely with this framework in mind that Aristotle makes his claim in *Metaphysics* B.1 that the search for scientific knowledge (ἐπιστήμη) ultimately involves going through the *aporai*—and in this, one may already get a glimpse of the object sought after.³⁷ In this, Pierre Aubenque observes well that Aristotle taps into the “existential” *aporia* that Plato dwells in, from the *Meno* and other dialogues, where the *aporia* is not just a “procedure” or “preparation” for investigation: it is rather in this state in which the investigation *itself* can only begin.³⁸ The impasse of the *aporia* for Aristotle becomes the condition for beginning and carrying through the

³⁵ Plato, *Meno* 80d5–8; trans. Grube.

³⁶ Aristotle, *Posterior Analytics* I.1, especially where Aristotle mentions the *Meno* by name in 71a29; see also II.19, 99b25–27. Cf. Politis (2003) 152, n. 13.

³⁷ See Politis (2003), esp. 150 ff., where he claims that the *Meno* background is essential to understand Aristotle's inquiry in the *Metaphysics* as an essentially aporetic one—and yet one that involves eventual resolution, *pace* Aubenque. See also Laks (2009) 44–45, esp.: “...there are good reasons to assume that what Socrates then reformulates as an ‘eristical argument’ constitutes the background of Aristotle's various justifications for the aporetical procedure, which may be construed as offering a systematic answer to the problem it raises. For these justifications are linked together by the question of how an inquiry can proceed under the condition of ignorance—ignorance of the impasse (the bond), ignorance of the goal of the inquiry (*agnoein* twice, and then *me gignoskein*). Aristotle's analysis of what an *aporia* is offers a kind of conceptual ‘coup’ consisting in making the impasse itself—quite different from any doctrine of reminiscence—the condition of its own overcoming: far from being reducible to what impedes the progression of thinking (for this is also what it is), it is, rather, the condition both of the starting of inquiry and of the obtaining and recognition of its solution.”

³⁸ Aubenque (1961) 5: “Ce dernier sens, où l'aporie désigne, non un procédé de recherche, ou même de préparation à la recherche, mais une situation existentielle dans laquelle le philosophe se trouverait plongé sans le vouloir, n'est autre, notons-le, que le sens socratique, selon lequel *aporia*, aporeit désignaient l'embarras de l'âme, déseparée ou «engourdie» après la réfutation par Socrate de ses prétendus savoirs, et aussi l'embarras de Socrate lui-même, conscient de son non-savoir.” Aubenque, beyond the *Meno* passage, also points to *Sophist* 244a, where Socrates observes that he and his interlocutors thought they knew what the word, “to be” (εἶναι), meant, but now are at a loss (νῦν δ' ἠπορήκαμεν); furthermore *Meno* 84a, *Theaetetus* 149a, *Gorgias* 522a–b, *Hippias Major* 297d, and *Lysis* 216c. Laks (2009) similarly picks up on this “existential” theme of *aporia* in his own reading of B.1's preface.

inquiry, from beginning to end—much the same way *aporia* seems to work in Socratic contexts like the *Meno* and other dialogues.³⁹

An additional element of Aristotle's stipulation is that not only must one "raise" or "experience" *aporiai* (ἀπορήσαι), but also take the next step of "developing the *aporiai* well" (διαπορήσαι καλῶς). Exactly how one should understand διαπορήσαι may be initially unclear—especially when one may be tempted to conflate the meaning of διαπορήσαι with ἀπορήσαι.⁴⁰ Rather, Aristotle's distinction between the two terms suggests that the state of *aporia* becomes understood and grasped in the process of "developing" the *aporiai*.⁴¹ Though he does not specify here what this process involves, it at least encompasses "topics" that cause, or raise, the state of *aporia*⁴²—including both topics that "certain people have supposed divergent things" and those which have been "overlooked". We may find some more specification of this process of "developing" the *aporiai* in the *Topics* (VI.6), where Aristotle critiques a problematic definition of *aporia* as indicating "equality between contrary arguments" (ἡ ἀπορία ἰσότης ἐναντίων λογισμῶν): for Aristotle, such a definition fails to include the referent or cause responsible for that attendant state or effect.⁴³ Rather, the state of equality between reasonings only results when one reflects on both sides of a given question and "finds everything alike to be in keeping with either course"—such that "we are perplexed which of the two we are to do."⁴⁴ The parallelism in cause and effect is then mirrored both in the epistemic state of the thinker as well as the given question, with its two possible answers, which triggers the *aporia*. This context should rule out understanding *aporia* in a purely subjective manner, i.e. that puzzlement is simply a feature of the inquirer; rather it reflects a difficulty in aspects of the object inquired, which mirrors the aporetic state of the inquirer at an impasse.⁴⁵ In turn, "developing the *aporiai*" (διαπορήσαι) would then involve going through the process of reasoning two opposite sides of the thesis

³⁹ On the claim that the *aporia* for Aristotle necessitates some inkling of its solution, see Laks (2009) 44–45. Aubenque (1961) 16–17, though, admits of certain, "extreme" cases where there does not appear to be any solution in *aporia* for Aristotle, in his sense (4): discussed below. See also Aubenque (2003) 8, implicitly referencing Socratic *aporia* with Aristotle's conception: "L'aporie est littéralement l'absence de chemin, mais aussi en même temps ce qui empêche le cheminement de se clore. Le fait de n'avoir pas de réponse à la question nous oblige à reposer la même question sous une autre forme ou à poser des questions adjacentes. L'aporie, qui est l'absence d'aboutissement, est en même temps le moteur du cheminement."

⁴⁰ Which, as Laks (2009) 32 observes, Alexander of Aphrodisias does in *In Met.* 171,11–14.

⁴¹ Laks (2009) 32–33, adapting the "existential" reading Aubenque (1961) 4–5 gives to the Socratic use of *aporia* (while disagreeing that Aristotle's sense of the term as a means or procedure).

⁴² Cf. Laks (2009) 39–40.

⁴³ Aristotle, *Topics* VI.6, 145a33–b5. In the passage the definition is one among a list of examples of imperfect definitions that Aristotle critiques, the others of which are "sleep as an incapacity to perceive" and "pain [which] is a violent disruption of parts naturally conjoined".

⁴⁴ Aristotle, *Topics* VI.6, 145b11–20.

⁴⁵ Following Politis (2003) 149, n. 7 (and with his elaborated thesis, 149 ff.) *pace* Aubenque (1961) 5, n. 5, that the *aporia* περί τοῦ πράγματος does not merely indicate the subject in his relation to the subject matter (πράγμα), but does rather indicate the subject matter in itself. See also Rapp (2018) 121–123 who analyzes *aporia* and dialectical *problēma*, which he argues are closely related to each other: "One possible explanation can be derived from the previously considered definition of the *aporia*. If an *aporia* is indeed thought to be the psychological state of puzzlement brought about by equal or equally strong reasonings, the dialectical problem would seem to be a problem that actually leads to such a state of puzzlement". Cf. Buddensiek (2018) 148 and below, n. 136.

(on the “objective” side) that triggers the *aporia*—both in putting together the two, opposing horns to a given position, as well as going through the argumentation in those two horns.⁴⁶

In the second paragraph of the passage, above, Aristotle connects the stage of “developing the *aporiai* well” (διαπορήσαι καλῶς) with the state, or outcome, of “advancing freely” (εὐπορήσαι / ἢ ὕστερον εὐπορία). How the two stages relate to each other, however, is not clear: is it when one finishes “developing the *aporiai*”, i.e. going through the arguments on both sides of a position, that this “free advance” is realized? If so, does this involve identifying the argumentative weakness in one or both horns and refuting one or the other horn—or does it involve a resolution in some other way? Or is it none of these—is it simply the *process* of διαπορήσαι, going through the *aporiai*, that is in itself the “free advance”? Addressing this question would also help to address the larger question of how or why the *aporiai* are necessary for the inquiry connected with the rest of the *Metaphysics*—why the state of *aporia*, and the need to go through aporetic arguments, is essential to the inquiry into the principles of being.

We can see by looking at the next half of Aristotle’s methodological passage in B.1:

That is why one must have gotten a theoretical grasp on all the difficulties beforehand, both for these reasons and because those who inquire without first developing the *aporiai* (διαπορήσαι) are like (a) people who do not know where they have to go. And, in addition, (b) a person [who has not already experienced the *aporiai*] does not even know whether he has found what he is inquiring into. For to someone like that the end is not clear, whereas to a person who has already experienced the *aporiai* (τῷ προηπορηκότι) it is clear. Further (c), a person is necessarily in a better position to make a judgment when—as if they were opposing parties in a court case—he has heard all the contending accounts. (995a33–b4; trans. Reeve, modified)

διὸ δεῖ τὰς δυσχερεῖας τεθεωρηκέναι πάσας πρότερον, τούτων τε χάριν καὶ διὰ τὸ τοὺς ζητοῦντας ἄνευ τοῦ διαπορήσαι πρῶτον ὁμοίους εἶναι τοῖς ποῖ δεῖ βαδίζειν ἄγνοοῦσι, καὶ πρὸς τούτοις οὐδ’ εἶ ποτε τὸ ζητούμενον εὔρηκεν ἢ μὴ γιγνώσκειν· τὸ γὰρ τέλος τούτῳ μὲν οὐ δῆλον τῷ δὲ προηπορηκότι δῆλον. ἔτι δὲ βέλτιον ἀνάγκη ἔχειν πρὸς τὸ κρίναι τὸν ὡσπερ ἀντιδίκων καὶ τῶν ἀμφισβητούντων λόγων ἀκηκοότα πάντων.

One thing we can first observe in this passage is the sense of directionality that Aristotle gives for one’s motivation to proceed through the *aporiai*: particularly (a) the direction to go and (b) the object to be sought. It is with these two factors in mind that Aristotle lists the negative consequences for not considering the *aporiai*: (a) not knowing where it is necessary to go (ποῖ δεῖ βαδίζειν), and (b) not knowing whether the object of inquiry has been found (εἶ ποτε τὸ ζητούμενον εὔρηκεν). One can see more strongly here the echoes of Plato’s *Meno* 80a–d, with Socrates and Meno realizing the paradox that they are in *aporia* while not knowing the object (i.e. virtue) that they are pursuing. Aristotle seems to be directly responding to this background in his claim that inquiry necessitates stimulating an aporetic state of mind through being made aware of the things causing *aporia*: hence “developing” the *aporiai*, i.e. going through the arguments on both sides of an issue, helps to bring out the contrasting issues in the object pursued. One is then able to proceed toward the object when the *aporia*

⁴⁶ Here I follow Rossi (2017)’s claim (esp. 233–255) that “the dialectic involved in Aristotle’s treatment of *aporiai* is not just the ability to find arguments or refutations of conflicting theses, which is developed through playing the role of the questioner in the dialogue [...] but also the critical ability to disarm an argument developed when responding in dialogue.”

is brought to the surface, through “developing” it in reviewing the arguments,⁴⁷ and in this way one gains an initial acquaintance with the object pursued—even within the state of being at an impasse in the *aporia*.⁴⁸

This brings us back to our question above: just what would the “resolution” of the *aporia* entail? To what degree is being in a state of “free advance” (εὐπορία) mutually exclusive with being in the state of *aporia*—or the process of it? As Aubenque has noted, εὐπορία throughout Aristotle’s works does not always imply (1) a simple resolution—such as negating a false argument in one or both of an *aporia*’s horns—but can involve at least three other cases: either (2) a resolution involving resorting to a plausible hypothesis, i.e. removing from the phenomenon in question “their irrational appearance” (e.g. in astronomical observations); (3) a resolution which implies that two opposing theses belong to the same phenomenon, and must be maintained in some sense, despite the apparent contradiction; or (4) rather no resolution—instead the *aporia* leads to “an indefinite search”, and is inherently irresolvable.⁴⁹ This last position would also go with Aubenque’s view—an outlier among other scholarly positions—that the inquiry into principles sought in the *Metaphysics* is impossible for humans: instead, the process of *aporia* is supposed to lead to a continual deepening and clarifying of the “essential” *aporia* or question(s) leading to the principles of being, reflected in the various times when Aristotle says we should begin the inquiry again (πάλιν δ’ ἐπισκεπτέον). While concurring with the majority position against Aubenque’s extreme claim in (4),⁵⁰ Aubenque’s interpretation does highlight the fact that some of the *aporai* are not trivial—as we will see particularly with the first *aporia* in *Met.* B.1. In any case, returning to the question of εὐπορία, Aubenque’s first three positions make clear that the “resolution” (λύσις) of the *aporai* has a number of possible meanings. Senses (2) and especially (3) suggest that the *aporia* is not done away with entirely when the resolution is reached, but instead the original *aporia* remains: the critical state engendered by the *aporia* becomes the condition for finding the resolution which still preserves the serious nature of the objective impasse or problem.⁵¹ This will be crucially important when we look at Damascius, where much of this sense of εὐπορία can also be found.

⁴⁷ Aristotle’s example at the end of the passage of the judge who hears “all the contending accounts” seems to imply that the procedure of going through the *aporai* is not so much about the force of the arguments in themselves, but rather the procedure itself. See Laks (2009) 41, who draws on the parallel judge imagery in *De Caelo* 279b7–12 to argue that, “the point being to take into account the efficacy of the procedure (*mallon d’an eie pista*) rather than the intrinsic force of the arguments.”

⁴⁸ See also Aubenque (1961) 8, showing how the *aporia* paradoxically keeps open the possibility of a path even when it makes clear the absence of a specific path: “L’aporie est littéralement l’absence de chemin, mais aussi en même temps ce qui empêche le cheminement de se clore. Le fait de n’avoir pas de réponse à la question nous oblige à reposer la même question sous une autre forme ou à poser des questions adjacentes. L’aporie, qui est l’absence d’aboutissement, est en même temps le moteur du cheminement.”

⁴⁹ Aubenque (1961) 13–17. See esp. for his sense (3), p. 15: “Un troisième cas est fourni par des apories dont la «solution» consiste, non à faire table rase des opinions discordantes pour laisser apparaître les *phainomena*, mais à reconnaître que les deux thèses opposées appartiennent l’une et l’autre aux *phainomena* et doivent donc être maintenues, du moins en un sens, en dépit de leur contradiction apparente.”

⁵⁰ Following Laks (2009) 40, Politis (2003), Buddensiek (2018) 146, Menn (forthcoming), et al.

⁵¹ Aubenque’s sense (3) goes well with Rossi (2017)’s argument of cases of *aporai* whose resolution (λύσις) does *not* imply refutation (ἔλεγχος) (esp. 215–224), where “a refutation is an argument against a single proposition or thesis, while a resolution is aimed against an argument” (215).

One further observation we can make, though not explicit in these passages, is that Aristotle's notion of *aporia* (and as we will see in the actual *aporiai*) is reflective of his dialectical method from the *Topics*.⁵² In *Topics* I.1, Aristotle defines the goal of his method as that by which “we shall be able to construct deductions from acceptable premises (ἐνδόξων) concerning any problem proposed, and—when submitting to argument ourselves—will not say anything inconsistent.”⁵³ Such a method is immensely useful insofar as it can be applied to any science with any set of premises, while aimed at the truth. In the case of the philosophical sciences, dialectic can discuss the principles of specific sciences on the basis of accepted opinions, where no particular science can establish or demonstrate its own principles in itself. In this context Aristotle also emphasizes the role of “developing the *aporiai*” (διαπορήσαι), on both sides of a given problem, so that one may “more readily discern the true as well as the false in any subject.”⁵⁴ Hence the dialectician is readily apt to engage in aporetic argumentation, where the collection of arguments in going through the *aporiai* helps one to better determine the truth about the principles in question. Applied to the *Metaphysics*, especially Book B, the aporetic method becomes one of the main ways in which the highest science with which the *Metaphysics* is concerned, i.e. wisdom, can assess its own principles. We will eventually return to some specific examples of Aristotle's dialectical method employed in *aporiai* further on.

To summarize briefly: Aristotle's preface at the beginning of *Metaphysics* B.1 gives us a framework in which he briefly spells out the roll of *aporiai* in the inquiry into the principles of being, at least in principle. One important factor is Aristotle's adaptation of the Platonic tradition (especially the *Meno*) in his own notion of *aporia*, especially as an impasse, and the necessity to become acquainted with arguments that lead to that state—and in the process, to discover the resolution (λύσις), which may have multiple manifestations. It is clear that Aristotle's aporetic methodology is far from being pedagogical, and that he takes seriously that some of the *aporiai* involve serious objections—and that their resolution may necessitate preserving the two, opposing sets of arguments for a position to be able to locate a solution beyond the initial tension. And even here, this does not imply leaving the critical, aporetic state of mind, which allows for finding a solution.

As we will shortly see, Damascius' *De Principiis*, especially in the case of the first *aporia*, bears the marks of Aristotle's methodological framework for the *aporiai* in Book B, especially in respect of its shared Platonic background and the sense of “resolution” (λύσις) implying the preservation of the initial aporetic difficulty. Though Damascius does not make his method explicit in the way Aristotle does, he does appear to treat the *De Principiis*' *aporiai* as the means to clarify what becomes his final stance on the principles and their different aspects. Like Aristotle, he takes up premises for the *aporiai* both from previous predecessors, as well as premises drawn by themselves without reference to any specific predecessor—like Aristotle's “overlooked” topics which his *aporiai* also aim at. In what exact ways we see this become elaborated in the next section.

⁵² Here I follow Rapp (2018), esp. 135–136, and Rossi (2017), especially interpreting the resolution (λύσις) of *aporiai* in the context of the dialectical procedure of resolution (λύσις) from *Topics* VIII.10 and the *Sophistic Refutations*.

⁵³ Aristotle, *Topics* I.1, 100a18–21; trans. Smith. Cf. Rapp (2018) 113–119.

⁵⁴ Aristotle, *Topics* I.2, 101a34–36; trans. Smith. See Rossi (2017) 227 ff., arguing for reading διαπορήσαι in the context of *Topics* I.2 as establishing arguments on one or both sides of an *aporia*, as an activity which leads to the final stage of resolution, and not as directly implying a refutation of one or the other thesis established around an *aporia*.

3. Damascius' Use of Aristotle's Aporetic Method

In this section I wish to focus mainly on the *De Principiis*' first *aporia* as a case study of Damascius' use of Aristotle for a few reasons.⁵⁵ First, as mentioned in Section 1, Damascius' first *aporia* establishes the broader theme for the rest of the *De Principiis* in juxtaposing the first principle in relation to its correlated effect, "all things" (τὰ πάντα). Though the *aporia* is aimed at the first principles over the intelligible realm (i.e. the One and the Ineffable), the problematic it establishes recurs in later *aporiai* on the various different levels of principles over all things. Secondly, most *aporiai* that Damascius raises involves an explicit resolution (λύσις),⁵⁶ while the first *aporia* is unique in that it does not offer an explicit λύσις as in the later, more conventional *aporiai*. As I will eventually argue, this bears similarities to the first *aporia* in Aristotle's *Metaphysics* B, which has been the subject of controversy in contemporary scholarship, and furthermore this fits with Aubenque's sense (3) of the resolution or "free advance" (εὐπορία) of an *aporia*. I will show how one recent reading of Aristotle's *aporia*—arguing that it is resolved in the much later, "theological" Book Λ—is parallel to the way that Damascius also "resolves" the first *aporia* later in the *De Principiis*. Though the final object of Damascius' *aporia* necessarily involves an entity which cannot be in any way defined, or even spoken (i.e. the "Ineffable"), it still forms part of the resolution that Damascius seeks in the correct articulation of first principles. As I will argue, Damascius' later articulation at the beginning of Volume II⁵⁷ of the *De Principiis* makes this explicit. This again points to the same intention by Aristotle as well in drafting the *aporiai* with the aim of providing a resolution in thought and articulation for the science of metaphysics—while yet utilizing the centrality of the state of *aporia* and the means of going through or "developing" aporetic arguments (διαπορήσαι) to continue the inquiry into metaphysics.

3.1. The First *aporiai* in Aristotle's *Metaphysics* B and Damascius' *De Principiis*

When we look at the first *aporia* raised at the beginning of the *De Principiis*, we are presented with two, contrary choices: either the "one first principle" (ἡ μία ἀρχή) (1) is "beyond" all things (τὰ πάντα), or it (2) "belongs with" all things. Damascius repeats the same two options from the perspective of "all things" (τὰ πάντα), which he

⁵⁵ I analyze this passage also in Greig (2021) 224–231, however mainly in comparing with Proclus' framework; here I focus on the Aristotelian background and context. For other analyses of this passage, among others see Caluori (2018); Vlad (2019) 22–37; Tanaseanu-Döbler (2016) 371 ff.; Ahbel-Rappe (1998), esp. 356–360; Rappe (2000), esp. 205 ff.; and Metry-Tresson (2012), esp. 41 ff.

⁵⁶ To give an example, one will tend to find critical or aporetic arguments raised against a given position—for instance, against the claim that it is true that the One is called "all things" (τὰ πάντα) in itself (*DPI*, 89,5–6, posed as a question: [τὸ ἔν] ὅπως ἀληθές ὅτι πάντα)—with Damascius responding with the adverb, ἦ ("we say...", "surely...", etc.) and his own reply to the question. (Hence from the previous example: after arguing against the proposition of the One as "all things", Damascius responds, "we respond that it is right to proclaim [the One] as all things" (*DPI*, 93,22: ἡ καὶ τούτων εὖ λεγομένων, ὀρθῶς ἔχει καὶ ἐκεῖνο πάντα ἀνυμνεῖν).) Other forms of this will be Damascius signaling, "for ourselves" (ἡμεῖς), e.g. when adjudicating Iamblichus' position in *DP* II, 16,4 ff.; or "one must resolve [the question]" (ἐπιλθετόν, in *DPI*, 96,16); and so on. Cf. Tanaseanu-Döbler (2016) 370–371.

⁵⁷ All volume numbers for the *De Principiis* are cited from the divisions of Westerink-Combès' edition.

appears to treat as synonymous to his first formulation when he goes through *aporia's* arguments. It is worth quoting his formulation of the two questions in full:

Is it the case that that which is called the one first principle of all things (ἡ μία τῶν πάντων ἀρχή) is (1) beyond all things, or (2) something belonging to all things—as it were, the summit of those things which proceed from it? And do we say that all things are (2*) together with it, or (1*) after it and from it? (1,4–7)

πότερον ἐπέκεινα τῶν πάντων ἐστὶν ἡ μία τῶν πάντων ἀρχή λεγομένη, ἢ τί τῶν πάντων, οἷον κορυφή τῶν ἀπ' αὐτῆς προϊόντων; καὶ τὰ πάντα σὺν αὐτῇ λέγομεν εἶναι, ἢ μετ' αὐτὴν καὶ ἀπ' αὐτῆς;

The first thing we may note here is how Damascius begins with “that which is called” (λεγομένη) the first principle. Various commentators have noted this feature, where Damascius begins not with the principle *in itself*, but what we say it is or what it is so-called (λεγομένη).⁵⁸ Though this largely reflects the vantage point of the person entering into the *aporia*, it can also reflect a definitional context. One can see this similarly, for instance, in the *Categories*, when Aristotle first discusses the category of substance (οὐσία): “That what is most chiefly, primarily, and most of all called (λεγομένη) ‘substance’ is what is neither said of a subject nor is in a subject” (οὐσία δὲ ἐστὶν ἡ κυριώτατά τε καὶ πρώτως καὶ μάλιστα λεγομένη, ἢ μήτε καθ' ὑποκειμένου τινὸς λέγεται μήτε ἐν ὑποκειμένῳ τινὶ ἐστίν).⁵⁹ In the case here with Damascius, it is in first defining the principle that we already are necessitated to demarcate its relation to all things (τὰ πάντα)—and hence trigger the two, opposing horns. Another, important aspect is the way that Damascius repeats the same question from the distinct perspectives of τὰ πάντα and the ἀρχή. By implication, answering either in the affirmative or in the negative for (1) [whether the ἀρχή is *beyond* τὰ πάντα] also affects its correlate, (1*) [whether τὰ πάντα is *below/after* the ἀρχή]—and similarly answering affirmatively or negatively (2) [whether the ἀρχή is *with/belongs to* τὰ πάντα] equally affects (2*) [whether τὰ πάντα is *with* the ἀρχή].⁶⁰ In other words, the *aporia* will equally affect both the status of τὰ πάντα *as well as* the ἀρχή.

As we find in the ensuing lines (1,8–2,20), Damascius sets up a number of arguments on contrary sides of the *aporia* he initially raises. To the latter question (1*), Damascius raises four reasons against this position—hence four reasons to say why τὰ πάντα are “with” the principle (1,8–2,8); and then to the subsequent question (2*), Damascius raises a *reductio ad absurdum* that τὰ πάντα would be without a cause and principle (ἀναίτιος, ἀναρχός), followed by an argument—proved to fail—that τὰ πάντα are either a principle or “from a principle”.

Damascius’ strategy of arguing negatively on both sides of the aporetic question raised mirrors Aristotle’s strategy in the *aporiai* of *Metaphysics* B.1, where arguments are stacked on both sides of a given position. The

⁵⁸ See e.g. Vlad (2019) 24–27, emphasizing the subjective aspect this implies.

⁵⁹ Aristotle, *Categories* 2a11–13.

⁶⁰ Damascius’ different phrasing for the relation between the ἀρχή and τὰ πάντα is significant: in (2), with the ἀρχή as “something belonging to” (τι τῶν πάντων), and in (2*) with τὰ πάντα as “together with” (σὺν αὐτῇ). In other words, Damascius seems to suggest that the ἀρχή is not something that is “together with” its correlate, τὰ πάντα, nor is the latter something that “belongs to” the ἀρχή. Hence, Damascius affirms there is an asymmetry between the two terms: they cannot be straightforwardly characterized as contraries, like “black” and “white” would be, insofar as one could apply the same description of relation of one color to the other. By contrast, the difference between τὰ πάντα and the ἀρχή would be similar to the correlated terms of parent and child, or ruler and ruled—as indeed Damascius makes explicit in *DPI*, 2,6–8.

first *aporia* is one prime example of this—beginning with the first statement in the introductory list of *aporiai* in *Met. B.1*:

The first *aporia* is concerned with the topic over which we developed a difficulty in our prefatory remarks, whether it belongs to one or several sciences (ἐπιστημῶν) to study the causes. (*Met. B.1*, 995b4–6)

ἔστι δ' ἀπορία πρώτη μὲν περὶ ὧν ἐν τοῖς πεφρομισασμένοις διηπορήσαμεν, πότερον μίας ἢ πολλῶν ἐπιστημῶν θεωρῆσαι τὰς αἰτίας·

Aristotle's mention of “the topic over which we developed a difficulty” alludes to his discussion in *Met. A* of wisdom (σοφία) as the constitutive science of metaphysics, or first philosophy, which is concerned with the first, highest cause or causes (singular or plural) of all beings.⁶¹ The question he takes up is whether wisdom involves one or *several* sciences corresponding to the differing causes of beings. At the outset Aristotle seems to refer to the four types of causes—i.e. material, formal, efficient, and final—though it quickly becomes apparent, when he later elaborates the *aporia*, that he could rather be referring to three of them (and not material), or perhaps just one of them, or perhaps other kinds of causes (for instance, the ten categories of beings, insofar as they could be construed as “causes”).⁶² In any case, we can see a parallel in both Aristotle's and Damascius' respective formulations: Aristotle argues two, contrary positions, with the question whether wisdom entails “one” (i.e. not-several) or “several” (i.e. not-one) sciences; and similarly, Damascius argues two, contrary positions with the question whether τὰ πάντα are “with” (i.e. not after) or “after” (i.e. not with) the first principle. Of course one main difference is that, in Aristotle's case, we were already supplied beforehand the premise that wisdom entails three or four types of causes (hence, more than one/several), e.g. as in *Metaphysics A*. In Damascius' case, we are only given the terms in the formulation of the initial question, without prior context. Furthermore in Aristotle, we do not have the kind of inverse formulation of the question that we saw in Damascius of (1) and (2) (i.e. whether the principle is before or with “all things”) together with (2*) and (1*) (i.e. whether “all things” are with or after the principle): for instance, we are not asked whether the causes belong to one or several sciences, or whether to some or no sciences. Yet regardless, the parallel in the general formulation may still stand.

⁶¹ Although whether this line refers to a *specific* passage or line that Aristotle discusses is not clear. In commenting on this line, C.D.C. Reeve (in Aristotle (2016) n. 253) notes that one might think the reference goes back to *Met. A.2*, 982b7–10, where Aristotle states that science being sought would investigate the primary principles and causes, including the good—though as Reeve also notes, Aristotle does not problematize this claim but merely states it. Reeve also points to the end of *α.3*, 995a8–20, just before *Met. B* as another possible source. Otherwise I generally follow Madigan (in Aristotle (1999) 26: “Presumably Aristotle is referring to *A.3–10*, and perhaps he regards the vindication of the completeness of the list of four causes in those chapters as an example of going through *aporia*.”) and Menn (Forthcoming) Iβ2c (“The first *aporia*”), 2: “But, while [*Metaphysics A*] *A* did not discuss whether there is a single science of different kinds of cause, *A3-7* had been an extended discussion of whether wisdom is a science of the material, the efficient, the formal or the final cause (and this is by far the most obvious ‘difficulty we discussed in the introduction’), and this is the discussion which Aristotle is now saying we must take up [...]” Cf. the discussion of this line in comparison with a similar formulation of the question in *B.2* (996a18–20) and *K.1* (1059a18–21) in Crubellier (2009) 47–49.

⁶² As recognized by Crubellier (2009) 48–49.

To see the underlying parallel in Aristotle's and Damascius' respective approaches in the purpose and aim of the *aporai*, including in their eventual, implicit resolutions, we should first compare the argumentative structures of the two *aporai*. Beginning with *Metaphysics* B's first *aporai*, we find the following structure:

- Horn (A) [996a20–b1]: Against the claim that wisdom pertains to **one** science to study the primary causes/principles.
 - Argument (1): How can one science study several objects (i.e. the principles) if they are not contraries (ἐναντία)? Hence, wisdom pertains to more than one science.⁶³
 - Argument (2):⁶⁴
 - (a) Wisdom pertains to all principles/causes;
 - (b) but not all causes pertain to all beings (e.g.: unchangeable beings seem to possess neither efficient nor final causality);⁶⁵ hence,
 - (c) wisdom (as one science) studies principles pertaining to some beings,
 - (d) but wisdom is concerned with all beings; consequently,
 - (d) wisdom pertains to more than one science.
- Horn (B) [996b1–25]: Against the claim that wisdom pertains to **several** sciences to study the primary causes/principles.
 - Primary reason [996b3–26]:

⁶³ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996a20–21.

⁶⁴ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996a21–36: “Further, there are many things to which not all the principles pertain. For how can a principle of change or the nature of the good be present in unchangeable things, since everything that in itself and by its own nature is good is an end, and a cause in the sense that for its sake the other things both come to be and are, and since an end or purpose is the end of some action, and all actions imply change; so that in unchangeable things this principle could not exist nor could there be a good-in-itself. This is why in mathematics nothing is proved by means of this kind of cause, nor is there any demonstration of this kind—'because it is better, or worse'; indeed no one even mentions anything of the kind. And so for this reason some of the Sophists, e.g. Aristippus, ridiculed mathematics; for in the arts, even in handicrafts, e.g. in carpentry and cobbling, the reason always given is 'because it is better, or worse', but the mathematical sciences take no account of goods and evils” (trans. Ross).

⁶⁵ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996a22–29 for unchangeable beings; a29–35 for mathematical objects—so they also would not have final causality. Crubellier (2009) 54–55 suggests a general Platonic background for this argument, of which this would then be a shortened summary of the different Platonist positions discussed in Book A—as a kind of early *διαπόρια*.

- (a) Wisdom has been described as one ruling science⁶⁶—hence it must pertain more properly to the individual science respectively belonging to either [i] the final cause,⁶⁷ [ii] the formal cause,⁶⁸ or [iii] the efficient cause;⁶⁹ but,
- (b) each of [i], [ii], and [iii] could equally correspond to the description of “wisdom”;⁷⁰ consequently,
- (c) none of the three causes’ respective sciences stand out as corresponding properly with “wisdom”;⁷¹ hence,
- (d) wisdom cannot pertain to “several” sciences.

In both Horns (A) and (B), Aristotle implicitly refers to the four kinds of causes—formal, material, efficient, and final—first elucidated in *Physics* II.3, and again at length in *Metaphysics* A.3 in connection with wisdom. This fact becomes important for Argument (1) in Horn (A), where Aristotle’s first objection against wisdom as one science of the four causes is that they are not contraries. The underlying assumption is that the unity of the wisdom’s subject matter must be defined in some other way, if it treats of multiple objects, rather than just one: hence the appeal to “contraries” as a criterion.⁷² How a definition involving more than one object can still be “one” is shown in *Topics* VI.9, where Aristotle argues that the unity of a definition can encompass multiple objects when they are contrary notions: for instance, knowledge and its contrary privation, ignorance; or for relatively-opposed terms, the definition of the double can encompass its relative corollary, the half, and so on.⁷³ As we will see, this is also an important principle in Damascius’ attempts to define the term, “all things” (τὰ πάντα), in relation to the first principle as either “together with” or “prior to” τὰ πάντα.

⁶⁶ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996b3–6, esp.: “For it is possible for all the types of causes to pertain to the same thing” (trans. Madigan); 996b10–12: “Insofar as wisdom is most directive and most controlling, and it is not right for the other sciences, like handmaids, to contradict it ...” (trans. Madigan).

⁶⁷ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996b10–13, esp.: “[Wisdom] is the science of the end, of the good, that is such, for the other things are for its sake” (trans. Madigan).

⁶⁸ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996b13–22, esp.: “But insofar as wisdom has been determined to be about the primary causes and what is most knowable, the science of essence would be such” (trans. Madigan).

⁶⁹ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996b22–24, esp.: “But as regards comings into being (γενέσεις) and doings (πράξεις) and every change, it is when we know the principle [or “beginning”] of motion” (trans. Madigan, modified). As commentators like Madigan note, Aristotle seems to leave out the possibility for a science of the fourth kind of “cause”, i.e. material causality. Perhaps Aristotle’s reference to wisdom as “most directive” and “most controlling” (above), this might *de facto* rule out the material cause, since it is purely passive in contrast to this description of wisdom.

⁷⁰ Aristotle, *Met.* B.2, 996b8–10: “On the basis of previous determinations about which science should be called wisdom, there is reason to term each of them wisdom” (trans. Madigan). I reverse the order of Aristotle’s presentation in the summarized argument: he begins with this statement, and then proceeds to show how each of the sciences of final, formal, and efficient causes could each bear the title of “wisdom”.

⁷¹ An additional argument stands out at the end of the passage, although it seems to do mainly with efficient and final causality, leaving out formal causality, at *Met.* B.2, 996b24–26: “But this [*scil.* wisdom as the science of the efficient cause] is different from and opposed to the end, so it would seem to be the task of another science to study each of these causes” (trans. Madigan).

⁷² Cf. Crubellier (2009) 51–52.

⁷³ See esp. Aristotle, *Topics* VI.9, 147a12–b26. Madigan’s commentary in Aristotle (1999) 34 also references *Prior Analytics* I.1, 24a21, although Aristotle there just cites the principle as an example.

In Argument (2) in Horn (A), the main underlying premise is that wisdom is concerned with all beings, while it was also established as concerned with all four causes. Hence, if only some causes pertain to certain sets of beings—as unchangeable and mathematical being, which appear to lack final causes—then there must be more than one science for wisdom: one for changeable beings, with all four causes, and at least one for unchangeable and mathematical beings, without final causality.

Aristotle’s strategy in Horn (B) is to show that, if wisdom pertains to multiple sciences—each corresponding to one of the four causes—there must still be one science among the several that relates best to wisdom, if wisdom implies priority among the other sciences. Still, however, each of the three sciences for final, formal, and efficient causality match the description of wisdom. This ultimately brings us back to the “one-science” position that Aristotle argues against from Horn (A)—which, on the terms we saw stated, also ends in impasse.

Turning to Damascius’ *aporia*, we also find an argumentative structure similar to Aristotle’s *aporia*. Damascius refutes one side of the aporetic horn—the principle as “beyond” all things, with four arguments—and then refutes the other horn—the principle as “beside” or “with” (παρά) all things:

- Horn (A*) [DPI I, 1,8–2,8]: Against the claim that all things (τὰ πάντα) are **posterior** to the “one principle of all things” (ἡ μία τῶν πάντων ἀρχή).
 - Argument (1*): Nothing is left out of the notion, “all things”: hence, the principle is also not left out of “all things”.⁷⁴
 - Argument (2*): “All things” means a multitude which is defined, or limited; nothing is *not* limited; hence the principle is included in the group of limited things as their “uppermost” extreme.⁷⁵
 - Argument (3*): The principle is coordinated (συντέτακται) with what is from it (*scil.* all things): hence the principle belongs with what it produces.⁷⁶
 - Argument (4*): “All things” indicates anything that we conceive (ἐννοοῦμεν); but the principle can also be conceived; hence, the principle is included with all things.⁷⁷
- Horn (B*) [DP I, 2,9–20]: Against the claim that all things (τὰ πάντα) are with (σὺν) the “one principle of all things”.
 - Primary reason: the notion of “principle” necessitates distinction from the set, “all things” (τὰ πάντα):

⁷⁴ Damascius, DPI I, 1,9–11: “For ‘all things’ (πάντα), in an unqualified sense (ἀπλῶς), are those from which nothing is lacking. But the principle is lacking, therefore all things are not absolutely after the principle, but beside the principle (παρὰ τὴν ἀρχήν).”

⁷⁵ Damascius, DPI I, 1,11–16: “Furthermore, ‘all things’ implies many things having been limited (τὰ πάντα πολλὰ βούλεται εἶναι πεπερασμένα), since the unlimited would not be completely all things. Therefore it is manifest that nothing is outside of all things: for totality is a certain boundary and thus an encompassment (ὄρος γὰρ τις ἢ παντότης καὶ ἤδη περιλήψις), in which the principle is, on the one hand, the upward limit (πέρας τὸ ἄνω), while the extreme of what is from the principle is the downward limit (πέρας τὸ κάτω). Therefore all things are with the limits.”

⁷⁶ Damascius, DPI I, 1,16–2,4: “And furthermore, the principle is coordinated (συντέτακται) with the things which are from it: for it is and is called the principle of those things. Both the cause then [is coordinated] with its effects, and the first with those things after the first. But we call these ‘all things’ which are a single coordination (μία σύνταξις) of those which are many, such that the principle is in all things.”

⁷⁷ Damascius, DPI I, 2,4–2,8: “And generally we say ‘all things’ in an absolute way (ἀπλῶς) so much as we conceive them in whatever way—but we also conceive the principle. Accordingly, we are even accustomed to call a ruler (ἄρχοντα) and those ruled (ἀρχομένους) the entire city (πάσαν πόλιν), and both begetter (γενήτορα) and those begotten (γεννηθέντας) the entire family (πάν γένος).”

- (a) The principle cannot be another item among all things, since the notion, “principle”, *de facto* implies distinction from “all things”. Thus “all things” as a coordinated structure (σύνταξις) are without a principle.⁷⁸
- (b) But everything must either (i) be a principle, or (ii) be from a principle. If (ii): the principle *de facto* is outside all things, not “with”; if (i): nothing proceeds from “all things”, since “all things” encompasses every entity [cf. *Argument (1*) above*]. Hence: all things are neither (i) a principle nor (ii) from a principle.⁷⁹

Similar to Aristotle’s aporetic argument above, Damascius argues against the two, opposed claims that all things are posterior to (and separate from) the first principle (Horn [A*]), and that all things are with the principle (Horn [B*]). Damascius gives four arguments for (A*) and—like Aristotle with Horn (B)—only one argument for (B*). One observation we can make in general is the way that Damascius relates the two terms of “principle” (ἀρχή) and “all things” (τὰ πάντα) in the *aporiai*: they are both correlated terms, defined in relation to each other, and yet, paradoxically, terms that necessitate distinction—in this sense *non*-correlated. The paradoxical difficulty in Damascius’ construal parallels the paradox in Aristotle’s case of giving a definition for “wisdom”, the constitutive science of first philosophy: as a science, wisdom should be correlated with one object, by the definition of a science, yet wisdom implies a plurality of objects, with the four causes; this would seem to imply multiple sciences for multiple objects, and yet one predominant science for wisdom still obtains.⁸⁰ In both Aristotle’s and Damascius’ construals, the two options mutually entail each other, just as they exclude each other—and hence trigger the paradox and ensuing state of *aporia*.

Arguments (1*)–(2*) effectively share the same premise. (1*)’s argument is that the notion, “all things”, is exhaustive of any items that are spoken of or referenced: though to say “principle” implies separation from that of which it is the principle—i.e. “all things”—the set of “all things” still implies the principle which is

⁷⁸ Damascius, *DPI*, 2,9–12: “If ‘all things’ are with the first principle, the principle is not something among all things, since [otherwise] even it has been comprehended in all things (συνειλημμένης ἐν τοῖς πᾶσι καὶ τῆς ἀρχῆς). Therefore, the single coordinated structure of all things (ἡ ἄρα μία τῶν πάντων σύνταξις), which [itself] we call ‘all things’, is without a principle (ἀναρχός) and without cause (ἀναίτιος), so that we do not go up upon the unlimited (ἵνα μὴ ἐπ’ ἄπειρον ἀνίωμεν).” Damascius’ claim that “we do not go up upon the unlimited” (μὴ ἐπ’ ἄπειρον ἀνίωμεν) parallels at least two similar formulations in Aristotle: in *Met.* α.2, 994a3, against an infinite series of material causes (“For neither is it possible for one thing to proceed from another to infinity (ἰέναι εἰς ἄπειρον) as matter ...”); similarly in 994a8, against an infinite series of final causes (οὐδὲ τὸ οὐ ἔνεκα εἰς ἄπειρον...ἰέναι), and 994a19–22, against an infinite series of formal causes [it would seem] (“Nor can there be an infinite process downwards, with a beginning in the upper direction (ἀλλὰ μὴν οὐδ’ ἐπι τὸ κάτω οἶόν τε εἰς ἄπειρον ἰέναι, τοῦ ἄνω ἔχοντος ἀρχήν), so that water should proceed from fire, earth from water, and so always some other kind should be produced”; trans. Ross, modified). One can see a distant echo in this last reference to Damascius’ own discussion of “upward” and “downward” directions of proceeding in relation to the infinite (which leads to absurdity in both cases): see next note.

⁷⁹ Damascius, *DPI*, 2,12–20: “But it is necessary that everything is either a principle or from a principle (πάν ἢ ἀρχὴν εἶναι ἢ ἀπ’ ἀρχῆς); therefore all things are either a principle or from a principle. However if the latter, the principle will not be with all things, but outside all things, because the principle is of those things from it (ἡ ἀρχὴ τῶν ἀπ’ ἀρχῆς); but if the former, what would proceed from all things, just as from the principle, and outside of all things toward the things downward as the full completion of all things (ἐπι τὰ κάτω ὡς τῶν πάντων ἀποτέλεσμα)? For even this is in all things, since the notion of ‘all things’ leaves aside absolutely nothing. Therefore, all things are neither a principle nor from a principle.”

⁸⁰ See below, sect. 3.2.

referenced. Damascius' reasoning is extended into Argument (2*), when he draws on the notion, found in Aristotle's *Metaphysics* α.2 and K.10,⁸¹ that there is no actual existence of the infinite or unlimited: *a fortiori* the cosmos, or the “all” (τὸ πᾶν), cannot be infinite but must, itself, be limited and defined.⁸² “All things” would then refer to a determinate number of entities, and nothing escapes that number. The principle must then be included in that group.

Along similar lines, Damascius in Arguments (3*)–(4*) emphasizes the role of coordination (σύνταξις) between the principle and all things as the motivation to place the principle “with” all things. While this is the main premise in Argument (3*), it is also in the background in Argument (4*)'s argument for the way we “conceive” (ἐννοοῦμεν) the principle together with all things. The point is illustrated rather distinctly in Damascius' examples: “Accordingly, we are even accustomed to call a ruler (ἄρχοντα) and those ruled (ἀρχομένους) the entire city (πᾶσαν πόλιν), and both begetter (γεννήτορα) and those begotten (γεννηθέντας) the entire family (πᾶν γένος).”⁸³ One sees the theme of contraries or relatively-opposed terms, from Aristotle above, come into the picture. The example of the “ruler” and “ruled” as constituting the city brings to mind Aristotle's description of definitions which include contrary or opposite terms. In *Topics* VI.4, Aristotle considers definitions where a term is defined through its opposite—for instance, good through evil: such definitions are simultaneous by their character, so that one cannot mention one without the other.⁸⁴ While “good” may be defined by itself, without reference to its opposite, evil, Aristotle mentions cases of definitions where opposed terms are necessitated in the definition, like the “double” and “half”, “and such terms which are, through themselves, so-called in relation to something else” (ὅσα καθ' αὐτὰ πρὸς τι λέγεται):⁸⁵

For in all such cases to be them is the same as to be in some way related to something, so that it is impossible to make known the one without the other, and accordingly in the account of the one,

⁸¹ Both passages in turn hearken back to *Physics* III.4–5 and 7, arguing against the actual existence of the infinite.

⁸² Vlad (2019) 28–29 points additionally to Plotinus' *Enn.* VI.6.3, 1–3, as an additional source for this notion. See also Westerink-Combès' commentary on the reference to Aristotle in their ed. in *DP* I,1, n. 2 (p. 131). Though the reference is brief, it is striking how Damascius appears to borrow this principle freely from Aristotle (if not just Plotinus) without explicitly taking account of the implicit anti-Platonic undertones of Aristotle's claim earlier in *Met.* K.10, e.g. in 1066a35–b21, against the idea of the unlimited as a substance or separable principle. Almost certainly in this latter discussion Aristotle has in mind the framework of the Limit and Unlimited from Plato's *Philebus*—principles which Damascius takes up himself in his metaphysics. Cf. Ross' commentary in Aristotle (1924) II, 331 ff.

⁸³ Damascius, *DPI*, 2,6–8: καὶ τοίνυν εἰώθαμεν πᾶσαν λέγειν πόλιν ἄρχοντα καὶ ἀρχομένους, καὶ πᾶν γένος τὸν τε γεννήτορα καὶ τοὺς γεννηθέντας. (Cf. above, n. 77.) The relation between “begetter” (γεννήτορα) and “begotten”, or “children” (γεννηθέντας), can be distantly found in Aristotle, *Met.* Δ.15, 1021a23–24, where Aristotle refers to the example of the “father is called ‘father’ of a son” (οὕτω γὰρ καὶ πατήρ υἱοῦ λέγεται πατήρ); the example is used for the case of things said to be “relative with reference to a capacity” (line 21 ff.).

⁸⁴ Aristotle, *Topics* VI.4, 142a22–24: “Of the failure to use terms that are prior there are three forms. The first is when an opposite has been defined through its opposite, e.g. good through evil; for opposites are always simultaneous by nature” (trans. Pickard-Cambridge). Of course in this case, defining “good” through its opposite, “evil”, is an example of a failure to make a definition to what is a prior term, like “good”, similar to failing to define through more familiar terms, like the infinite through what is defined: cf. the previous 142a17–21.

⁸⁵ Aristotle, *Topics* VI.4, 142a28. The co-relation of opposed terms like “double” and “half” are discussed by Aristotle in other passages, e.g. *Categories* X, 1b24–31, and *Met.* Δ.15, 1020b26–1021a14.

the other too must be embraced together (συμπεριελήφθαι).⁸⁶ (*Topics* VI.4, 142a28–31; trans. Pickard-Cambridge, modified)

πάσι γὰρ τοῖς τοιοῦτοις ταῦτόν τὸ εἶναι τῷ πρὸς τί πως ἔχειν, ὥστ' ἀδύνατον ἄνευ θατέρου θάτερον γνωρίζειν· διόπερ ἀναγκαῖον ἐν τῷ τοῦ ἑτέρου λόγῳ συμπεριελήφθαι καὶ θάτερον.

Damascius appears to have this passage in mind when he draws out in Arguments (3*) and (4*) why the first principle should be construed in relation with “all things”: if one is giving a definition of the set of all things (τὰ πάντα), following Aristotle’s premise that a definition should include both terms that are “prior” and terms that are “more familiar” (προτέρων καὶ γνωριμωτέρων),⁸⁷ then the principle must necessarily be included as the prior in the definition, alongside “all things” as the more familiar term. In other words, the principle (ἡ ἀρχή) and all things (τὰ πάντα) entail each other, as co-relative terms.

Along these lines, Damascius’ example of conceiving the city as including ruler (ἄρχοντα) and ruled (ἀρχομένους) brings to mind Aristotle’s metaphor in *Metaphysics* Λ.10 of the army (στράτευμα) with its order (τάξις) and the general over the order (στρατηγός).⁸⁸ Aristotle uses this metaphor for his claim that the good found in the “nature of the whole”, or cosmos (ἡ τοῦ ὅλου φύσις), is not solely in “that which is separated and itself-by-itself” (κεχωρισμένον τι καὶ αὐτὸ καθ’ αὐτό), nor solely in the order (τάξις) subsequent to it, but rather in both. The army metaphor shows how the good is in both aspects, as both the army general and his order, although “more” (μᾶλλον) in the general. As Damascius will elaborate soon after the *aporia*, he also characterizes the first principle—in the capacity of the One—as also “more” all things (πάντα) than “all things” in themselves; in turn, both the principle and all things equally share the same attribute—just like the attribute of “the good and the best”, for Aristotle, belonging to both the principle (ἀρχή) and the beings in its order.⁸⁹ Finally, Aristotle’s claim in *Metaphysics* Λ.10 that all things are “jointly ordered together in relation to one thing” (πρὸς μὲν γὰρ ἐν ἅπαντα συντέτακται) is also reminiscent in Damascius’ claim in Argument (3*) of the principle being

⁸⁶ Compare Aristotle’s use of συμπεριλαμβάνω in this context with Damascius’ use of συλλαμβάνω in *DPI*, 2,9–10, where the first principle (ἀρχή) “has been comprehended in all things” (συνειλημμένης ἐν τοῖς πάσι καὶ τῆς ἀρχῆς). Both use middle-passive, perfect forms of λαμβάνω, and both use the prefix, συν-, while only Aristotle also uses the prefix, περι-. I take it that, despite Aristotle’s additional prefix, περι-, the definitional context in both is the same—and all the more so, where both talk about relatively opposed terms being captured in their definitional contexts.

⁸⁷ Cf. *Topics* VI.4, 141a23–b14, esp. b1–2. The distinction between the two is echoed throughout Aristotle’s works—more well-known e.g. in *Physics* I.1, 184a17–21, where the science of nature is supposed to proceed from what is “more familiar and clearer to us” (γνωριμωτέρων ἡμῖν) to what is “more familiar and clearer by nature” (σαφέστερα τῇ φύσει καὶ γνωριμώτερα). See also, from *Topics* VI.4, 141b15–17: “Absolutely, then, it is better to try to come to know what is posterior through what is prior, inasmuch as such a way of procedure is more scientific” (trans. Pickard-Cambridge). (Ἀπλῶς μὲν οὖν βέλτιον τὸ διὰ τῶν προτέρων τὰ ὕστερα πειρᾶσθαι γνωρίζειν· ἐπιστημονικώτερον γὰρ τὸ τοιοῦτόν ἐστιν.)

⁸⁸ Aristotle, *Met.* Λ.10, 1075a11–25, esp. 11–15.

⁸⁹ For Damascius, cf. e.g. *DPI*, 3,10–12; 94,9–12. For Aristotle, cf. *Met.* Λ.10, 1075a14–15.

coordinated (συντέτακται) with all things.⁹⁰ All these cases show how Damascius appears to have a conceptual framework similar to Aristotle's *Metaphysics* Λ.10 in mind when he argues for the principle's "coordination" in Arguments (3*)–(4*) and uses examples like the ruler and ruled constituting the city, as well as parent and child constituting the family. These cases all go back to Aristotle's emphasis on the necessity to include relatively opposed terms in definitions, as above in *Topics* VI.4. Damascius then seems to be trying to find a way in Horn (A*) to show how a science of all things is possible—namely in the sense that knowing "all things" means knowing its cause, i.e. the principle—which hence necessitates including the principle "with" all things.

Yet as one finds in Horn (B*), taking the definition of "principle" (ἀρχή) raises a serious difficulty for including "principle" with the group of "all things". In the first lines of the *aporia*'s second horn, Damascius maintains that "the principle is not something among all things", where, if all things were considered "with" the principle, the principle would be "comprehended" (συνειλημμένης) with them.⁹¹ On the one hand, the very attempt to isolate the notion of "principle" from "all things" from the beginning already implies a distinction which, straightforwardly, already negates the including the term "principle" with "all things". Yet coming out of an Aristotelian context in talking about causes, why this is a problem may not be obvious: is it not natural to include the principle with its effect, albeit construed as a cause? In this sense, Damascius may be considering a sharper sense of distinction, or exclusion, in the term, "principle". Though this premise is unstated, Damascius could have in mind Aristotle's fourth notion of "principle" (ἀρχή) from *Metaphysics* Δ.1 as "that from which (ὄθεν) a thing first comes to be (*not* as existing in the thing [μὴ ἐνυπάρχοντος])."⁹² The other senses of "principle" in Δ.1 all focus on that "from which" (ὄθεν) something is, while the fourth sense specifically entails that "principle" is *not* part of the thing or effect in question—in contrast to cases such as, for instance, the point that is the "principle" or beginning of a line, which is *also* part of the line. Hence in this case, Damascius highlights the problem of defining the principle "with" all things in a way that implies it is ἐνυπάρχοντος with "all things"—in contradiction to its status as *not* ἐνυπάρχοντος. If the definition of "principle" in this latter sense is taken seriously, then "all things" cannot be so defined with the principle.

⁹⁰ Aristotle, *Met.* Λ.10, 1075a16–23, esp.: "For all things are coordinated in some way, although not in the same way—even swimming creatures, flying creatures, and plants. And the order is not such that one thing has no relation to another but rather there is a relation. For all things are coordinated in relation to one thing [...]" (trans. Reeve, modified). (πάντα δὲ συντέτακται πως, ἀλλ' οὐχ ὁμοίως, καὶ πλωτὰ καὶ πτηνὰ καὶ φυτὰ· καὶ οὐχ οὕτως ἔχει ὥστε μὴ εἶναι θατέρω πρὸς θάτερον μηδὲν, ἀλλ' ἔστι τι. πρὸς μὲν γὰρ ἐν ἅπαντα συντέτακται [...].) It is noteworthy in this context that Aristotle *does not* include the good-itself (i.e. the principle, or unmoved mover(s)) in the order itself, although the good-itself is referenced as that "toward which" the other items are oriented. Still, given that the attribute of the "good" is shared between both the principle and "all things", they would then fall under the same science of the good: so Stephen Menn argues. On this cf. e.g. Menn (Forthcoming) Iβ2c, 20–22, where he defends an interpretation of Aristotle, *Met.* B's first *aporia*, with the *aporia* being solved in *Met.* Λ.10. (On this passage in relation to Plato on the Good, see Menn (1992).) Cf. the discussion of "coordination" in the first *aporia* in Vlad (2019) 29–31; see esp. 30 n.3, where Vlad also references Plato's *Republic* V, 462c–d, which refers to the living organism as a coordination of body and soul—shown to be a metaphor for the city.

⁹¹ Cf. above n. 86 for the definitional context of συνειλημμένης.

⁹² 1013a7–8: ἡ δὲ ὄθεν γίνεταί πρῶτον μὴ ἐνυπάρχοντος καὶ ὄθεν πρῶτον ἡ κίνησις πέφυκεν ἄρχεσθαι καὶ ἡ μεταβολή, οἷον τὸ τέκνον ἐκ τοῦ πατρὸς καὶ τῆς μητρὸς καὶ ἡ μάχη ἐκ τῆς λοιδορίας.

This leads to Damascius' conclusion that "all things" are "without principle and without cause,"⁹³ which in turn leads to his subsequent argument that "all things", despite Aristotle's claim in *Physics* III.4, can "neither be a principle nor be from a principle" (τὰ ἅρα πάντα οὔτε ἀρχὴ οὔτε ἀπ' ἀρχῆς).⁹⁴ This last conclusion already implies its own *aporia*: how can there be "all things" which are without a principle, nor themselves a principle? Nevertheless it highlights the aporetic conclusion of taking Arguments (B*) and (A*) together: one cannot simply assert the principle as either "with" all things, or "before" all things. The impasse of this *aporia* requires a new way of proceeding.

3.2. Comparing the First *aporiai* and their "Free Advances" (εὐπορία) in the *Metaphysics* and *De Principiis I*

We should now take stock of our analysis of the two first *aporiai* in the *De Principiis* and *Metaphysics* B. Both end at an impasse: in Aristotle's case, we cannot determine whether there is *one* science or *several* sciences for wisdom in relation to the four causes; in Damascius' case, we cannot determine whether the first principle is *with* or *before* all things. The series of arguments against the position of one horn leads to the other horn, and the series of argument against the other horn leads one back again to the first—which was already negated: one ends in an impasse, in which it is impossible to choose either alternative. Thus, in both cases there is no determinate answer that can be given within the parameters of the *aporia's* two horns—and indeed, they induce the state of aporetic impasse which is their intended purpose, as Aristotle sets out in the preface of *Metaphysics* B.1.

Part of attempting to determine the function of the *aporia*—whether it can even be resolved definitively—is to see how it is implicitly or explicitly addressed later on. In other words, one needs to see in what sense there is or can be a resolution (λύσις), and whether the subsequent state of "advancing freely" (εὐπορία) entails a resolution, or, as has been noted above, whether that simply means the process of searching can merely continue. Here we may find a parallel in Aristotle's and Damascius' respective approaches, where it is only in further investigating the terms involved in the *aporiai*, and through their refinement, that a resolution is eventually reached. What I propose here specifically is that the λύσις offered to Aristotle's and Damascius' respective *aporiai* roughly fits the third sense of εὐπορία offered by Aubenque in commenting on Aristotle: both horns contain a share of the truth in relation to the object sought after, but the refutation (or acceptance) of one

⁹³ Caluori (2018) 271–272 reads Horn (B*) as claiming that "the whole of reality (including its principle) either has no principle or we end up in an infinite regress". However, Damascius does not himself seem to draw this second conclusion of an infinite regress, but rather he seems to be referencing his earlier claim that there is nothing beyond what is limited, i.e. "all things": to go beyond this, i.e. into the infinite, when there is no infinite, would be absurd (cf. *DPI* I, 1,12: ἵνα μὴ ἐπ' ἀπειρον ἀνωμεν)—hence the definitional impasse. Later in the *De Principiis* Damascius treats the One as the final stop for a potential infinite regress in the second "ascent" to the first principle in *DPI* I, 54,6–17: what triggers the search for a principle above the One is the One's possession of the faint reflection of opposite characteristics (μετὰ τῆς τῶν ἐναντίων ἐμφάσεως), i.e. of being unknowable and knowable, ineffable and able to be spoken, such that it cannot qualify as absolutely "first", i.e. without opposites in any regard (56,8–12).

⁹⁴ Cf. above n. 79.

in exclusion to the other is not possible—something beyond the two is needed, but in a way that preserves the *aporia*.⁹⁵

In the case of Aristotle, despite the fact that most of the other *aporai* discussed in *Metaphysics* B are determinately answered to one degree or another (as discussed earlier), the first *aporia* stands out as not having one, clear-cut, determined answer afterward in the *Metaphysics*. Whether and/or where Aristotle ultimately answers this *aporia* has been a subject of dispute in contemporary literature,⁹⁶ but we can mention at least two positions.⁹⁷ Commentators like W.D. Ross claim that the *aporia* is generally answered in *Metaphysics* Γ.1–2, where Aristotle claims that metaphysics studies all the causes or principles of being *qua* being: inasmuch as the causes are related as *pros hen* equivocal terms to one term, i.e. substance, the theoretical answer to the *aporia* is that wisdom ultimately studies one “object”, substance, which implies the other causes through their *pros hen* relation with substance.⁹⁸

Stephen Menn, however, has argued against this reading by pointing out that *Metaphysics* Γ.1–2 does not address the specific terms of the *aporia* (as Ross concedes),⁹⁹ thus arguing that the *aporia* is not truly answered there or in other passages such as *Physics* II.7.¹⁰⁰ Instead, the *aporia* is finally answered in *Metaphysics* Λ.10, when Aristotle addresses the question of how the good is found in “the nature of the whole”—as discussed in the last section. In Λ.10, while addressing Anaxagoras’ position, Aristotle claims that the “good” not only moves as an efficient cause (as Anaxagoras maintains), but it is also a final cause (as Anaxagoras fails to maintain). To

⁹⁵ Hence Aubenque (1961) 15: “Dans ce cas, il faut admettre que l'aporie ne tient pas, ou ne tient pas seulement à une défaillance du raisonnement, mais que l'aporie du discours révèle adéquatement une pluralité d'aspects dans la chose elle-même: pour saisir la chose, autant que possible, dans sa totalité, il faut alors se garder de trancher entre les thèses en présence et reconnaître qu'elles comportent chacune une part de vérité”; see also n. 26 in Aubenque.

⁹⁶ Indeed, Aubenque seems to think *aporai* like the first one in *Met.* B.1 do not have any solution, insofar as they relate to essential questions such as “what is being?” (e.g. in (1961) 16, referencing *Met.* Z.1, 1028b2)—in other words the core of Aristotle's project in the *Metaphysics*, which for Aubenque is inherently aporetic in this sense (cf. (1966) 508). Hence *aporai* of this kind for Aubenque rather fit under his sense (4) for εὐπορία, discussed above.

⁹⁷ A kind of *tertium quid* between these two positions of Ross et al. and Menn is Crubellier (2009) 61–62, where he references *Met.* A.7 as the implicit resolution to the first *aporia*, where Aristotle claims that the unmoved mover moves as an object of desire and intellect. Crubellier takes this to mean that three of the four kinds of causes—final, efficient, and formal—merge into one object with the unmoved mover, insofar as efficient and final causality fit the mover's description as an object of desire, while formal causality fits the mover's description as an intelligible object—while material causality is also implied, insofar as form implies its corresponding matter. This would in some way reconcile the position of Ross and others, in holding that wisdom concerns the four causes, with the position of Menn, in holding that wisdom corresponds to the unmoved mover, with the causes converging in the mover (though unlike Menn, who holds that wisdom only concerns efficient and final causality).

⁹⁸ See Ross' commentary in Aristotle (1924) I, 227. See also Madigan's commentary, discussing Ross' and others' interpretations in Aristotle (1999) 39–40.

⁹⁹ Cf. Ross' commentary in Aristotle (1924) I, 227: “Aristotle answers the question in Γ.1, by saying that metaphysics studies all the causes or principles of being *qua* being. The precise difficulties raised here, however, are not solved.”

¹⁰⁰ See esp. *Physics* II.7, 198a22–32, where Aristotle claims that the three kinds of cause—formal, final, and efficient—coincide. Menn cites Décarie (1961) 97, who rejects Ross' and others' claim, while citing the *Physics* passage. Yet Menn argues also against this Décarie's claim, since the *Physics* passage only deals with the objects of natural science, whereas *Met.* B's first *aporia* raises the difficulty of considering unmoved/unchanging objects (which lack a material, and—on Menn's reading—formal, cause) together with objects in motion. On this cf. Menn (Forthcoming) Iβ2c, 2; 12 ff.

the degree that both causes coincide in the separated “good”, i.e. the unmoved mover of *Metaphysics* Λ.6–7, this effectively addresses the *aporia* on wisdom studying one or several causes, on Menn’s reading: in effect, wisdom pertains to “several” causes, namely two—efficient and final—yet the two kinds of cause coincide in one object—namely the unmoved mover.¹⁰¹ Though it is beyond the scope of this paper to analyze and/or argue for Menn’s interpretation, one benefit of this reading is that it shows how the eventual solution to the *aporia* comes about only after Aristotle posits and discusses the first, unmoved mover in *Metaphysics* Λ. It is in showing the requirements of the first mover, and to what degree certain of the causes do not apply to the mover (namely formal and material), that we get a reconfiguration of the kinds of “primary causes” pertinent to the first mover as the highest good—like the good that is “more in the general than in the army-order”.

Hence on a reading like Menn’s, the first *aporia* in *Metaphysics* B is resolved by a reconsideration of the primary being or principle to which the four causes pertain, and the kinds (and number) of causes which pertain to the primary principle. If we consider a reading like Menn’s in light of the different senses of the resulting “free advance” (εὐπορία) discussed above, Aubenque’s third sense of the εὐπορία is suggested: neither of the original *aporia*’s horns are refuted, but neither does Aristotle simply accept one or the other horn without modifying the premises. As it turns out, Aristotle accepts that wisdom is indeed one science—but its object is one entity, i.e. the unmoved mover, wherein two of the four kinds of causes coincide. The *aporia* is still preserved, inasmuch as the problem of the plurality of kinds of causes in connection with whether one science can encompass them still remains. The final resolution (λύσις), as Aubenque notes, depends on the preservation of the premises of the two horns of the *aporia*, from which a new solution can be sketched.

In the case of Damascius’ *aporia*, we do not find a clear, conventional passage or place where the *aporia* is resolved, like Aristotle’s *aporia* above. Yet in another way, one sees a certain parallel to Aristotle’s approach insofar as the ultimate answer we *do* find to the first *aporia* is the result of a dialectical investigation into the nature of “all things” (τὰ πάντα), followed by how “principle” (ἀρχή) can (or cannot) be enunciated in its strict sense. We see this immediately after the first *aporia* in *DPI*, 2,21–4,12, where Damascius claims that all things are seen in some form of distinction and plurality (ἐν πλῆθει πως ὁρᾶται καὶ τινι διακρίσει).¹⁰² On asking how this plurality emerges, Damascius posits three categories, or modes, in which “all things” are conceived: (1) all things as they are immediately manifest in distinction and plurality; (2) all things unified in the monad—undifferentiated, but still characterized by plurality; and (3) all things in pure simplicity and unity, i.e. the One, with neither plurality nor differentiation.¹⁰³ Previous Neoplatonists would claim that this last category, the One,

¹⁰¹ Cf. Menn (Forthcoming) Iβ2c, 19–22. On Aristotle’s critique of Anaxagoras, see *Met.* Λ.10, 1075b8–13. This would be similar to Crubellier’s position in n. 97.

¹⁰² The language of appearing or being “seen” (ὁρᾶται) once again connects with Damascius’ language earlier of “what is called the one first principle” (ἡ μία τῶν πάντων ἀρχή λεγομένη). Vlad (2019) 32–33 relates passages like this in the *aporia* as relating to the soul’s state of perceiving things in plurality and distinction—and hence the place of the *aporia*. While agreeing with this, I would add that Damascius does also seem committed to the real plurality and distinction that unfolds in the entities and principles that correlate with “all things” (τὰ πάντα): i.e. the plurality of gods/henads, Intellect containing a real plurality of Forms, etc. In this respect, the soul’s state of *aporia* reflects an objective *aporia* in the class of “all things”.

¹⁰³ Damascius, *DPI*, 2,23–3,12.

is the first principle *per se*, and nothing further is needed.¹⁰⁴ It is however at this point that Damascius poses a key, dialectical question: if “all things” are equated with plurality, then the two principles of the unified (2) and (especially, or primarily) the One (3) are principles of “all things”;¹⁰⁵ yet if the One is defined or comprehended as “all things”, insofar as it is conceived as the cause of all things *absolutely*, it will then be in coordination with “all things” (implicitly [1] and [2] again)—hence the conclusion, “our argument searches for another principle before all things.”¹⁰⁶ Damascius’ dialectical response indicates the two aspects in which “principle” should now be considered: either as relative to “all things” under the aspect of their manifested plurality (i.e., the One),¹⁰⁷ or as relative to “all things” *absolutely* (i.e., “another principle”).¹⁰⁸ Although hinted here as the result of two dialectical considerations, Damascius develops the scaffolding of his formal answer to the problem of the principle’s relation to “all things” in the ensuing pages of *De Principiis* I: on the one hand, the One ([3] above) is the “principle” of all things, considered in respect of their plurality, hence “with” all things; on the other hand, if considering the principle of “all things” *absolutely*, another “principle” must be posited—i.e. the “Ineffable”, as Damascius later calls it.

Though one may be tempted to say that simply positing these two principles solves the *aporia*, it is quite clear the *aporia*, in itself, is not resolved in a straightforward manner: no refutation of one or the other horn occurs, nor is the solution framed as a simple combination of the positions of both horns (i.e. as simply both “with” and “before”). Instead the *aporia* remains, namely the duality that conditions “all things” (τὰ πάντα) and any notion of the principle in relation to that. Hence, the context of the *aporia* helps to highlight the problem of

¹⁰⁴ Damascius points this out explicitly in his doxographical survey of previous Neoplatonists on the number of principles in relation to the intelligible triad in *DP* II, 1,8–11; discussed more below. See also Proclus, *Elements of Theology*, Prop. 11 (among other passages), esp. 12,32–33: “For that there is one, single principle (μίαν τὴν ἀρχὴν) has already been shown, inasmuch as every plurality exists as secondary to the One” (trans. Dodds, modified).

¹⁰⁵ Damascius, *DP* I, 3,18–21.

¹⁰⁶ Damascius, *DP* I, 3,21–25: “But if we were also to conceive these entities [i.e. the unified and the One as principles of ‘all things’ in distinction] as all things (πάντα), and if we were to comprehend [them] together (συλλάβοιμεν) with the rest of ‘all things’ (τοῖς ἄλλοις πᾶσι) according to both relation and coordination in relation to them [i.e. the ‘rest’], as was (again) stated earlier, then our argument searches for another principle before all things, which it is not even fitting to know as ‘all things’ nor to coordinate together with the things from it”. (εἰ δὲ καὶ ταῦτα ὡς πάντα ἐννοήσαιμεν καὶ τοῖς ἄλλοις πᾶσι συλλάβοιμεν κατὰ τὴν πρὸς αὐτὰ σχέσιν τε καὶ σύνταξιν, ὡς εἴρηται καὶ πρότερον, ἐπιζητήσει ἡμῖν ὁ λόγος ἀρχὴν ἑτέραν πρὸ τῶν πάντων, ἣν οὐκ ἄξιον ἔστι πάντα νοεῖν οὐδὲ συντάττειν τοῖς ἀπ’ αὐτῆς.) Note Damascius’ use of συλλαμβάνω (in its optative form), yet again reminiscent of its definitional context: see above n. 86.

¹⁰⁷ See Vlad (2019) 39–49, who considers Damascius’ initial conclusion of the One as the principle of all things/τὰ πάντα in *DP* I, 2,23–3,21, as a “tentative exit” from the *aporia*—before the dialectical qualification is triggered. In particular, see 49, where she concludes that the One as “all things before all” (πάντα πρὸ τῶν πάντων), “...échappe ainsi aux apories, car il n’est ni dans le tout, ni hors du tout. On pourrait dire aussi l’inverse: en effet, «l’un-tout avant le tout» est avec le tout, mais sans s’identifier à quelque chose dans le tout, ou avec le tout ensemble; de même, il est au-delà du tout, mais sans être hors du tout. «L’un-tout avant le tout» est la cause du tout, parce qu’il est tout. En même temps, il est antérieur au tout, parce qu’il précède la pluralité du tout et qu’il la résorbe. Il est au-delà, non pas parce qu’il serait au dehors de la pluralité du tout, mais parce qu’il réduit cette pluralité à l’unité.”

¹⁰⁸ See Vlad (2019) 55–59, who sees, in the return of the aporetic difficulty in *DP* I, 3,21–4,12 ff., a second “exit” out of the initial *aporia*, by preserving the difficulty of the *aporia* as an indicator of thought’s duality (and hence weakness), and using it as a means to reach the absolute principle before the all (τὰ πάντα)—i.e. the “other principle”, or Ineffable.

duality in the soul's perception of the principle and "all things"—and simultaneously the *aporia* reflects the ontological state of duality affecting "all things", up to the One in itself. This initial intuition is carried forward by Damascius in his dialectical consideration, above, which leads him to distinguish between the Ineffable and the One, with the One as what is "principally both cause and the first" (τὸ κυρίως αἰτιόν τε καὶ πρῶτον) over all things (τὰ πάντα),¹⁰⁹ while the Ineffable as the entirely uncoordinated (ἀσύντακτον), beyond cause and effect (implicitly the One and plurality).¹¹⁰ Consequently, the discussion of the two terms, "principle" and "all things", requires a re-orientation around the notion of duality, and how much thought in itself—and "all things", as the object of thinking—is itself characterized by duality. This brings us back to *Meno* 80a–d again, with Meno asking Socrates how they will recognize or know the thing that they do not know—what is the cause of their state of *aporia*. Damascius' *aporia* then seems to follow in the spirit of Aristotle's methodology in the sense that "developing the *aporia*" (διαπορήσαι), i.e. going through the argumentation of the two horns, makes us aware of the condition of duality affecting the soul in its search for the principle of "all things". The "free advance" (εὐπορία) then means accounting for this duality in the soul's attempt toward the principle of "all things"—which is either their summit, i.e. the One, or the absolute principle, which is beyond the summit and entirely uncoordinated, i.e. the Ineffable. In turn, providing a discourse to talk about these levels of reality—while preserving the valid difficulty engendered by the *aporia*—becomes an important key for the εὐπορία.¹¹¹

What I would hence like to suggest is that the first *aporia* Damascius does imply a resolution, or εὐπορία: on the one hand it is the soul becoming aware of its ontological state; on the other, it is also recognizing the need to posit two principles, i.e. the Ineffable and the One, to be able to explain the reality of "all things". This resolution still preserves the original *aporia*, both in the valid conclusions it draws and the state of impasse it triggers—in much the same way, in broad outline, that Aristotle's own resolution does. The distinction Damascius draws between the Ineffable and the One cannot be simply characterized as "before" and "with" all things, from the *aporia*, even though one may be tempted to: for instance the One might be construed as "with" all things (as the first cause), and the Ineffable as "before" all things (as uncoordinated). But Damascius' *aporia* makes clear the impossibility of a straightforward identification with these two alternatives: his clarification of the levels of duality that obtain in "all things" (τὰ πάντα) illustrates the paradox involved in talking about the Ineffable as a principle beyond the level of language and thought, or concept (ἔννοια),¹¹² conditioned its position at the level of

¹⁰⁹ Damascius, *DP* I, 5,10–13.

¹¹⁰ Damascius, *DP* I, 6,16–7,4.

¹¹¹ Here I agree in part with Metry-Tresson (2012) in her description of the "euporetic experience of *aporia*" (82–89), where she claims that εὐπορία for Damascius lies in accepting the "le fait aporétique lui-même" (i.e. the impossibility to decide the relation of "principle" and "all things") and ascending to the level of the Ineffable. Yet I would add, beyond this, the importance of the use of words, and ways to articulate the means to go beyond the "fact of the *aporia*": hence, I would argue, the εὐπορία for Damascius also involves the correct articulation of this "ascent". This can be the only justification I see for why Damascius switches to an objective perspective on the principles and their number in *De Principiis* II–III.

¹¹² See e.g. Damascius, *DP* I, 16,15–17.

τὰ πάντα, in duality.¹¹³ In turn, even talking about the One involves a paradox, where, although conditioned by duality as the “summit” of all things, the One's simplicity implies that straightforward language also cannot refer to it adequately.¹¹⁴ To discuss or refer to the Ineffable, even if negatively, already implies an “overturning” (περιτροπή), because one has spoken of that which cannot be spoken of, referred to, or indicated.¹¹⁵ Yet one is still necessitated to discuss and become aware of the Ineffable in investigating the principles of “all things”.¹¹⁶ Furthermore the thinking soul still bears the “birth-pangs” and intuition, or divining (μαντεύεται), of something further than can be indicated in any of these ways.¹¹⁷ To use Marilena Vlad's terminology, Damascius employs “para-discursive means” to indicate the Ineffable, where the weakness and duality of human concepts and language become the means by which the soul recognizes and turns toward the Ineffable.¹¹⁸ It is these “means” which allow us to refer to the Ineffable as the absolute principle “before” all things—even while self-consciously accepting that this cannot be literally spoken.¹¹⁹ Hence, although Damascius' discussion of the Ineffable is centered around the limitations of thought, and the ways in which thought can transcend itself to reach the absolute principle, these “para-discursive means” allow Damascius to utilize the Ineffable in his metaphysical

¹¹³ In this additional respect I agree with Caluori (2018) that the *aporia* is meant to reveal “certain crucial epistemic limitations” and also point “to a reality that is beyond the grasp of language and reason”. Although I would still highlight the external, objective aspect of that limitation manifested in the *aporia*, viz. in the Ineffable in juxtaposition to all things (τὰ πάντα), as I argue here.

¹¹⁴ Among other places, see e.g. *DPI*, 74,7–76,2.

¹¹⁵ See e.g. Damascius *DPI*, 8,12–20. Vlad (2019) 141–179 argues that Damascius' use of περιτροπή is the key signifier for “indicating” the Ineffable, i.e. for bringing the soul into the state of being “aware” of the Ineffable; see also Greig (2021) 281–282, 295–302. Cf. Metry-Tresson (2012) 35–39, Caluori (2018) 280–282, and Castagnoli (2010) 244–247, especially with the useful term, “operational self-refutation”, for indicating Damascius' usage.

¹¹⁶ After the first *aporia* in *DPI*, 1–2, and the discussion of the Ineffable in 3–26, Damascius in *DPI*, 27–61, posits three “ascents”, or quasi-proofs, for the Ineffable as the first principle by going through the differing levels of Neoplatonic principles, from body/nature to Soul, Intellect, and the One—all three ending in demonstrating something higher than the One, and the resulting “overturning” in speech corresponding to the Ineffable. As Tanaseanu-Döbler (2016) 389 concludes on the ascents, these indicate that the Ineffable is still an essential part of Damascius' system, *pace* Rappe (2000): “Die drei Aufstiegswege deuten an, dass Damaskios über das Postulat der Notwendigkeit des relationslosen Prinzips der Wirklichkeit, das strenggenommen kein Prinzip im Sinne einer Ursache sein darf, doch das Bedürfnis verspürt, dieses Prinzip in das Gefüge der Wirklichkeit als höchste Stufe zurückzubinden und Methoden der Vergewisserung und der schrittweisen geistigen Annäherung für die philosophische Meditation zu skizzieren. Diese Aufstiegswege zeigen, dass es im System einen unbestimmten Übergang gibt—die ‘Umfassungsmauer’ des Einen,” die den Bruch zwischen Wirklichkeit und ἀπόρητον markiert. Insgesamt bilde das System aber doch ein beschreibbares geordnetes Ganzes—das Erste eingeschlossen”.

¹¹⁷ On the soul “divining” the Ineffable, see Damascius, *DPI*, 4,13–15. See also Vlad (2019) 67–80, where the soul's “divining” follows directly on the soul's impasse in the *aporia* between the first principle and “all things”: for Vlad, the “divining” which reveals the Ineffable as simply uncoordinated (ἀσύνηκτον) is also what brings the soul directly into contact with the Ineffable.

¹¹⁸ See Vlad (2019) 61 (with 123–126) where she refers to Damascius' use of the metaphors of “divining” (μαντεύεται), “suppression” of discourse and passing into “nothingness” (τὸ οὐδέν), and “birth-laboring” (ὠδίζ) as the “moyens para-discursifs” by which the soul aims at the Ineffable.

¹¹⁹ In turn, Damascius' later clarification of referring to the One “by analogy” (κατὰ ἀναλογία) allows us to talk about the One beyond the horizon of duality without collapsing it into being simply “with” (or “before”) all things: see e.g. *DPI*, 127,19–130,3. On this passage and analogical predication for the One, see Greig (2021) 257–265.

hierarchy: as he later shows, the Ineffable is the condition for the One's position and causality, as the “sanctuary” (ἄδυτον) of the One and as guaranteeing its transcendence,¹²⁰ while it also functions as the transcendent echo (and in one sense, “principle”) of matter, which is beyond the One's domain of effects.¹²¹ Hence it becomes a principle that Damascius repeatedly appeals to in his metaphysics, even when it cannot be called “principle” without qualification.

One problem with recent interpretations of Damascius' first *aporia* is that most appear not to reconcile the *aporia* with Damascius' objective reading and use of the Ineffable later in the *De Principiis* (especially Volume II) and in his other works. The majority tend to emphasize the subjective aspect of the *aporia*, in certain cases to a degree that denies the objective correlate of the problem—as well as its resolution. In this light, it would clearly be a mistake to see Damascius' *aporia* as either destructive of the idea of a first principle, or as tending to a suspension of judgment (ἐποχή). In Sarah Rappe's reading, for instance, the *aporia* serves as a denial of the first principle, or the One, in light of Damascius' use of the Skeptical critiques of causation, where the cause must pre-exist its effects, but a cause cannot be such without simultaneously being in relation to its effects. On this interpretation, the *aporia* is irresolvable and meant to lead one to a suspension of judgment on the metaphysical status of the first principle in Damascius' system.¹²² Yet as we have seen, and will see below, Damascius seems to do the opposite and rather embrace the notion of principle—albeit a principle beyond duality.

Others like Carolle Metry-Tresson see the *aporia* as oriented around the limits of the thinking subject, thus playing a pedagogical role in providing self-knowledge for the soul in its relation to principles which are inaccessible “realities”.¹²³ Metry-Tresson qualifies the first *aporia* as a “meta-dialectical *aporia*”, where constructions of this type imply a radical incompatibility between the two horns: as a result they necessitate transcending dialectic and speech.¹²⁴ The first *aporia*, as falling under this category, hence implies no true resolution (λύσις): instead, the subsequent “free advance” (ἐπόρεια) from the *aporia* for Metry-Tresson lies in the

¹²⁰ Cf. Damascius, *DPI* I, 56,8–16, where he speaks of the One possessing its own transcendence and ineffability “by participation” (κατὰ μέθεξις) from the “first”—i.e. the Ineffable. On this passage, cf. Combès (1989) 218 and Greig (2021) 289–290.

¹²¹ See e.g. Damascius, *In Parm.* IV, 68,8–19 and 72,3–8. Cf. Greig (2021) 302–304 and Van Riel (2011) 197–202.

¹²² Ahbel-Rappe (1998), esp. 356–360. For a critical assessment of Rappe's position, see Tanaseanu-Döbler (2016), esp. 367–371.

¹²³ See e.g. Metry-Tresson (2012) 66–67, alongside a similar interpretation in Galpérine (1987) 25. A roughly parallel to Metry-Tresson's reading is Caluori (2018)'s interpretation of the first *aporia*, where the *aporia* is inherently irresolvable (and hence not an Aristotelian-style *aporia*, as a starting point of inquiry: cf. p. 269), and is meant to illustrate the boundaries of epistemic reason, corresponding to the Ineffable's metaphysical (and linguistic) status.

¹²⁴ Metry-Tresson (2012) 66–69. See esp., 67: “Ces apories métadialectiques sont celles qui soumettent la question du Principe (premier/absolu) et de son rapport avec le tout (tout / tout absolu) et dont émerge un conit et une impasse qui ne peuvent être résolus ni par la pensée elle-même ni par aucune stratégie de la pensée. La première aporie du *Péri Archôn* [scil. *De Principiis*] est de cet ordre. [...] Mais cette exigence qui nous tiraille ne renvoie à aucun «objet», à aucun métaconcept ni à un quelconque point d'appui pour la pensée. Le drame est d' autant plus cruel que la pensée est mue par un impératif qui va bien au-delà de l'intellection et qu'elle ne peut donc atteindre et penser.” By contrast, “dialectical” *aporia* for Metry-Tresson involves an explicit resolution (λύσις) of the initial *aporia*, and involves an exercise (γυμναζόμεναι) of bringing a plurality and division of concepts into unity: see 59–66.

soul's "acceptance" of this aporetic fact, and in deepening the knowledge of its limits in self-knowledge.¹²⁵ It is notable how Metry-Tresson's interpretation seems to fall close to sense (3) or—more likely—(4) of Aubenque's εὐπορία schema for Aristotle, especially where the *aporia* for Metry-Tresson serves a pedagogical purpose in inculcating self-knowledge for the soul—regardless of the Ineffable's separate existence by itself. It is also notable that Metry-Tresson glosses Aristotle's notion of *aporia*, particularly in *Metaphysics* B.1, as a "zetetic tool" oriented towards an external object, and hence implying resolution, without the other possible interpretations of Aristotle's *aporiai* that are not so straightforwardly resolvable.¹²⁶ In any case, a general problem with those like Metry-Tresson's reading is that, though she is certainly right about the *aporia*'s pedagogical purpose for the soul, it does not explain well Damascius' later references to the Ineffable as a distinct, objective principle—born as the result of the first *aporia*'s conclusion of the inherent limitations of the soul, or rather the duality characterizing "all things" (τὰ πάντα). How the *aporia* would connect to this objective context remains an open question.

In this regard, Marilena Vlad's reading fits better with the subjective and objective aspects of the issue, insofar as the first *aporia* for Vlad both illustrates the limitations of discursive thought in its duality, and, at the same time, provides a step toward utilizing those limitations to become the means for thought transcend itself and meet the Ineffable.¹²⁷ Hence, while her reading agrees with Metry-Tresson in respect of the pedagogical aim of the *aporia*, i.e. to train the soul to realize its limitations, Vlad's interpretation is more positive in claiming that the Ineffable can be "indicated" by the "para-discursive means" (discussed earlier) that the discursive soul must realize, after the *aporia*. Vlad's reading would then fit more closely with a more "objective" reading of the *aporia*—but one that still affirms the limitations of thought, or duality, in itself that indicates an objective reality beyond concepts and words.¹²⁸

Bringing Vlad's reading together with the parallels to Aristotle, noted above, what I want to suggest here is that there is a kind of resolution (λῦσις) in the *De Principiis*' first *aporia*—albeit not a standard λῦσις which completely resolves the *aporia* in itself. What this resolution amounts to is both a purification of our concepts—

¹²⁵ See above n. 111.

¹²⁶ Metry-Tresson (2012) 31, 56. It is noteworthy that Metry-Tresson does not consider Aubenque's interpretation of the essential *aporiai* in Aristotle's *Metaphysics* as irresolvable and thus, similarly, "pedagogical" for the inquirer continually searching—much like her reading of Damascius' "essential" *aporiai* like the first in *DP* I, 1–2.

¹²⁷ See e.g. Vlad (2019) 24 ff., esp. 32–33.

¹²⁸ Here I also take Combès (1989)'s "theological aporetic" reading in this sense, insofar as the *aporia* points to an objective reality that thought cannot ascertain in itself—hence "theological" insofar as the Ineffable grounds the One and the gods. (See e.g. 202–203: "L'association des termes théologie et aporétique n'est pas contradictoire. L'aporétisme de Damascius ne vise pas à ruiner la croyance mystique de l'apophasisme néoplatonicien par un nihilisme qui serait un athéisme déclaré, [...] L'aporétisme de Damascius ne se présente pas, non plus, comme un scepticisme détaché, ou même inquiet, à l'égard du dépôt sacré, et qui aboutirait à un athéisme larvé. Quand le ton laisse apparaître une certaine angoisse et perplexité, ce ne sont pas celles du doute, mais du tourment mystique sous le discours déchiré.") Along a similar objective, "theological" line of interpretation is Butler (2019), though in a very different key: for him the *aporia* points to the "ineffable", albeit as the condition for the henads, or gods, altogether and in themselves. As I understand Butler's reading, which follows on his reading of Proclus, only the gods/henads are the truly existent "first" principle(s), hence they fill the position of the "One": Damascius' Ineffable then clarifies the impossibility of grasping the gods altogether, while each is manifest in the procession of Being (see 31–33).

which still works within the aporetic frame established in *De Princ.* I, 1–2—and a parallel re-orienting in how we describe reality, namely the principles and their attributes. As the first *aporia* makes clear, attribution in terms of duality is no longer possible: however, the first, true principle is still attainable (hence “indicated”) after the soul’s purification of duality, especially in its self-conscious realization of overturning (περιτροπή);¹²⁹ similarly, the One, as also without duality in itself, is still able to be indicated by analogy (κατὰ ἀναλογίαν).¹³⁰ The fact that Damascius uses this backdrop to make objective judgments in *De Principiis* II against his predecessors on the types and number of principles—especially in distinguishing the Ineffable and the One—suggests that Damascius himself sees a kind of resolution to the question of the first principle’s relation to “all things” from his discussion in Volume I. This however means being consciously and critically aware of the reality of duality in speech and thought, and the need to contextualize just how the absolute first principle (i.e. the Ineffable) is referred to—and also how the first cause below the absolute principle (i.e. the One) is discussed. This is however speech that ultimately fits the “para-discursive” frame, while it still preserves the basic difficulty of the first *aporia*.

It is here where I would argue that we can draw a general parallel to the εὐπορία of Aristotle’s first *aporia* in *Metaphysics* B, on Menn’s reading earlier. Just as Damascius’ *aporia* leads to a reevaluation of the terms, “all things” and “principle”, so Aristotle’s *aporia* leads to a reevaluation of wisdom as a science, the object of that science, and the kinds of causes that wisdom is concerned with. The original difficulty of the *aporai* in both cases is rather not left behind: instead the impasses they impose lead to a resolution that goes beyond the terms of both horns of the original *aporia*—in this sense both keeping with Aubenque’s sense (3) of εὐπορία. Hence, like Aristotle’s *aporia* leading to an eventual, determinate solution, Damascius’ *aporia* also leads to a determinate solution in distinguishing the Ineffable and the One, although in a very distinct, contextualized way. This becomes apparent when one looks later at the beginning of Volume II of the *De Principiis*, where Damascius discusses his predecessors’ positions on the structure of principles in relation to the intelligible triad: it is here where he makes clearer the initial results on the Ineffable and the One from *DP* I, 2–4, as we will discuss in the next section.

3.3. *Dialectical Premises in Damascius’ aporiai*

One remaining consideration is the content that gives rise to the opposing positions in the *De Principiis*’ first *aporia*. This reflects the dialectical nature of the premises taken up, which, as discussed earlier, finds its roots in Aristotle’s framework, and which are also applied in *Metaphysics* B’s first *aporia*. Once more the parallel between these two is apt, where the dialectical premises in these two *aporai* set the agenda for the later discussion and resolution, when those premises are ultimately reassessed.¹³¹

¹²⁹ See earlier n. 115.

¹³⁰ See earlier n. 119.

¹³¹ Here I simply use the term, “dialectic”, in the sense Aristotle defines in juxtaposition to Metry-Tresson’s notion of “dialectical *aporia*”, which she contrasts with what she calls the “meta-dialectical *aporia*”: see above n. 124.

One may first note that Damascius rarely, if ever, names any particular philosophical figure or position in *De Principiis* I,¹³² in contrast to Volumes II and III. This is also rather marked in Volume I's first *aporia*, where Damascius does not name any specific position or figure in the premises used. As noted earlier, one also finds no philosophical figures or their positions cited explicitly in *Metaphysics* B's *aporiai*. By contrast, Aristotle in the earlier Book A explicitly cites specific figures, like the Presocratic “naturalists”—Anaxagoras, Thales, etc.—Pythagoreans, Eleatic Monists like Parmenides, and the Platonists. In dialectically addressing their positions in *Metaphysics* A.3–9, one might think that Aristotle could gather the premises needed to proceed with the project of metaphysics: why go through a new set of premises in *Metaphysics* B's *aporiai* that, in at least certain cases, could go back to positions held by previous philosophers already discussed? Recalling again the methodological preface in *Metaphysics* B.1, though Aristotle mentions the importance of going over “topics about which people have supposed divergent things”, he also mentions the importance of topics which “may have been overlooked.”¹³³ Hence the topics, and thus premises, used in the *aporiai* represent a new beginning, especially insofar as the questions posed by the *aporiai* are ones previous figures may not have asked. They set the agenda for the rest of the *Metaphysics* in how to address questions both about the science of wisdom and its objects (as seen in the first *aporia*), as well as the specific nature of the principles in question, before one can provide a full answer to other previous philosophical positions and the problems they imply—for instance, as we saw in *Metaphysics* Λ.10.

When looking at the *De Principiis*' first *aporia*, it would be a mistake to see Damascius transparently applying Porphyry's position, for example, to one of the claims he considers—i.e. whether all things are “together with” the first principle, rather than after it—or also Iamblichus' and/or Proclus' position of the One as “before” all things. Of course it is not as if Damascius' predecessors are absent from the background of the first *aporia*—Damascius will eventually raise their positions explicitly in the beginning of Volume II. But here in the beginning Damascius appears to be using the first *aporia* and the ensuing *aporiai* in Volume I, much like Aristotle in *Metaphysics* B, as a way to orient the inquiry on the first principle and its connection to “all things” (τὰ πάντα), which leads eventually to his inquiry into the nature of the two principles of the Ineffable and the One—where neither can be cleanly described in their relation to “all things” as simply “with” or simply “before” them.

Why is this so? What are the reasons for these contrasting, opposing positions that arise and generate the *aporiai*? With *Metaphysics* B, insofar as the *aporiai* pertain to aspects of being, or the primary causes and the sciences concerning them, one could say that the objects in themselves do not directly imply conflicting views or positions: rather, certain elusive features of the objects also lend themselves to different, conflicting

¹³² There are a few notable exceptions in *De Principiis* I: Plato, whose name shows up 25 times; Aristotle, who is named four times; and Speusippus once, in *DP* I, 3.9. Barring these exceptions, and more to the point, it is notable that Damascius does not name any more recent Platonists—especially pertinent in Volumes II and III.

¹³³ Aristotle, *Met.* B.1, 995a25–26. Cf. Buddensiek (2018) 140–142. Buddensiek (141, n.9) also notes one specific example in the tenth *aporia* (*Met.* B.4, 1000a5–1001a3) where Aristotle states: “No less a puzzle than any has been passed over both by people now and by previous ones, namely, whether the principles of things that can pass away and things that cannot pass away are the same or distinct” (1000a5–7; trans. Reeve, modified).

perspectives.¹³⁴ This would fit with Aristotle's example from *Topics* VI.6 of one definition of *aporia* as a state or disposition of puzzlement resulting from weighing contrary arguments or thoughts, rather than the contrary thoughts in themselves,¹³⁵ even though Aristotle does not seem interested simply in the subjective, psychological state alone.

The *aporai* would then be ways to define more precisely the problem arising from the opposing positions that can arise, both among pre-existing philosophical positions and also positions not yet considered, arising from the objects of inquiry in themselves. One can see Aristotle's preface on the *aporai* in *Metaphysics* B as an application of what he terms a "dialectical problem", from *Topics* I.11, which is directed toward choice or determining the truth about an object of speculation, about which "people either have no opinion, or the public think the opposite of the wise, or the wise think the opposite of the public, or each of these groups has opposed opinions within itself."¹³⁶ *Aporai*, especially the variety Aristotle is interested in, then fall into this latter category, i.e. as the resulting state of juxtaposed arguments of equal weight on both sides, aimed ultimately at knowledge or truth. The premises used in dialectical problems, implicitly including *aporai*, involve reputable opinions or positions (*endoxa*)¹³⁷ that could be acceptable to the majority of people or the wise (whether all, the most famous, or a majority):¹³⁸ such premises, though plausible, need not be true in themselves, even though they aim at truth. Hence, such *endoxa* can (and often do, for Aristotle) also imply contrary opinions, even ones that are also *endoxa*: for instance, what is the opposite of *endoxon* for X is *adoxon* (i.e. without repute) for X, yet may become *endoxon* for Y.¹³⁹ Applying this framework to *Metaphysics* B's first *aporia*, the premise that Horn (A) attacks (i.e. that there is *one* science for the primary causes) would then be *endoxon*, with good reasons for it from the arguments made in Horn (B). At the same time, the *endoxon* Horn (A) attacks also implies its contrary position which Horn (B) attacks (i.e. there are *many* sciences for the primary causes)—and which could also be considered as *endoxon*. One can then see how Aristotle's dialectical structure contextualizes his construal of *aporai* and the opposing dialectical premises that they consider.

In turn, Damascius' *aporai* similarly imply aspects of Aristotle's dialectical structure. If we look back at the first *aporia*, though Damascius does not use terms like *endoxon* or *doxa* (i.e. opinion) to describe the argument's premises, we find the claims critiqued in both Horns (A*) and (B*) ones that could count as *endoxon*, or

¹³⁴ Buddensiek (2018) 145–147.

¹³⁵ See earlier, n. 43. Cf. Rapp (2018) 120–121.

¹³⁶ Aristotle, *Topics* I.11, 104b1–5; trans. Pickard-Cambridge. Cf. Rapp (2018), esp. 130–133 on the definition of the dialectical problem.

¹³⁷ Cf. Aristotle, *Topics* I.1, 100a18–21, in relation to the definition of dialectical method for the *Topics*; cf. Rapp (2018) 113–115. Interestingly, it should be noted that there is occurrence of ἐνδόξον or any of its derivatives in Damascius' corpus (on doing a word search in the TLG database), in contrast to Aristotle.

¹³⁸ Aristotle, *Topics* I.14, 105a34–b1; cf. Rapp (2018) 125–127.

¹³⁹ Aristotle, *Rhetoric* II.25, 1402a33–34: "For the deductions are taken from accepted opinions, and (such) opinions often contradict each other" (trans. Rapp); see also *Topics* VIII.5, 159b4–6: "If the thesis is unacceptable, then, the conclusion must become acceptable, and if acceptable unacceptable (for the questioner always concludes the opposite of the thesis)" (trans. Smith). See also Rapp (2018) 127–129, esp. 128 on how the opposite of what is *endoxon*-for-x can be *endoxon*-for-y while *adoxon*-for-x.

reputable: one finds strong reasons in Horn (A*) (attacking the claim of the principle “before” all things) to assert why to associate the principle “with” all things; and in Horn (B*) one finds a clear, self-evident reason to maintain the principle as “before” all things, by considering the definition of “principle”, especially as not existing in (ἐνυπάρχοντος) the thing of which it is a principle.¹⁴⁰ Though the major premises considered in both Horns are not associated with any specific philosopher or position, both could certainly be acceptable either to the wise or even by common perception (corresponding to the “majority of people” above). Damascius seems to appeal particularly to the latter in the way he talks about how “we” perceive and conceive of things, implicitly the source of the premises he begins the first *aporia* with. And, in turn, it is from these common conceptions that the *aporia* arises when squaring the two horns with each other.

We find a noticeable claim in connection with the source of the Horns’ premises, after the first *aporia*, where Damascius distinguishes the three senses of “all things” (τὰ πάντα):

Furthermore, all things are seen together in a certain way (πως) in plurality and a certain distinction. For we do not conceive (ἐννοοῦμεν) the all without these features. (*DP I*, 2,21–22)

ἔτι δὲ τὰ πάντα ὁμοῦ ἐν πλήθει πως ὁρᾶται καὶ τινι διακρίσει· καὶ γὰρ τὸ πᾶν οὐκ ἄνευ τούτων ἐννοοῦμεν.

Damascius establishes that any concept (ἔννοια) we have concerning the “all” (τὸ πᾶν)¹⁴¹ necessarily involves distinction and plurality. This becomes an important axiom when he next clarifies the nature of “all things” (τὸ πᾶν, τὰ πάντα),¹⁴² which do not exist in plurality and distinction alone but also imply two extra categories: the “unified”, which lacks distinction but still implies plurality; and the One, which lacks both distinction and plurality.¹⁴³ Soon after, Damascius shows that to claim the One’s unity, as “more one than all things” and in juxtaposition to “all things” in themselves, already results in duality posited in the One.¹⁴⁴ As Damascius concludes, “the ones dividing are ourselves, and it is ourselves who are doubled concerning its simplicity, and who are yet multiplied.”¹⁴⁵ Putting this together with Damascius’ claim that we conceive or think in terms of distinction and plurality, this conditions how objects appear to us: concepts, properly speaking, pertain to

¹⁴⁰ Cf. earlier, n. 92.

¹⁴¹ The term, τὸ πᾶν, could either be translated as “all” in a generic sense—so it could, for instance, stand in for “all things” (τὰ πάντα) in Damascius’ use of the term—or it could also reflect the common Greek term for the universe/cosmos. In the case of Damascius, I interpret it here as a correlate of τὰ πάντα, to refer to “all” generically—notably, here, in the singular case than Damascius’ typical plural usage.

¹⁴² In my reading I treat the two terms, τὸ πᾶν and τὰ πάντα, as effectively synonymous with each other, although see Butler (2019) 127 who maintains a crucial distinction between the two: “*Ta panta*, ‘all things’, are not presented at the outset as problematic, and so his problem is not whether, or why, there is something rather than nothing, but rather the integrity of totality, by virtue of which we say *to pân*, the All. Indeed, whereas Proclus preferentially uses *to pân* in discussing the determination of totality, which emerges through the intellectual activity of the Gods (i.e., in the third intelligible triad), Damascius shows a marked preference for *ta panta*.”

¹⁴³ Damascius, *DP I*, 2,23–3,2.

¹⁴⁴ Damascius, *DP I*, 4,1–6.

¹⁴⁵ Damascius, *DP I*, 4,6–8: ἡμεῖς δὲ οἱ μερίζοντες καὶ περὶ τὴν ἐκείνου ἀπλότητα διπλασιαζόμενοι καὶ ἔτι πολλαπλασιαζόμενοι.

determined objects.¹⁴⁶ Thus, when talking about or conceiving the first principle, as if it were a distinct item apart from “all things” (which implies other distinct items), one imports the characteristic of distinction into the object of that conception. Because such duality is necessarily implied in concepts, this results in a conflict with the reality of the thing in itself, especially if the thing lacks the characteristic feature of concepts, i.e. distinctions.¹⁴⁷ This in turn leads to conflicting initial perceptions about the principles under investigation, a confusion which, without the right contextualization, leads one to describe the intelligible realm and the principles in improper or incorrect ways. Concepts (ἔννοιαι) for Damascius become the content for the *endoxa*, or premises, found in the *aporiai*. Hence the *aporiai* make explicit the possible ways that lead to conflict, with the opposing positions they go over, and the ways forward in better construing the principles. This, yet again, ties in with Aristotle’s dialectical framework, where the *endoxa* involved in dialectical problems, especially in *aporiai*, lend themselves to opposing positions: here Damascius seems to see the concepts (ἔννοιαι), tied to Aristotle’s *endoxa*, as corresponding to the ontological reality of the lowest level of “all things”, i.e. in their distinction and plurality.

As a final example of incorrect yet reputable *endoxa* taken up dialectically, we can look back at the parallel between Aristotle and Damascius in the way that they address specific philosophers and their problematic positions after their respective *aporiai*. In Aristotle’s case, the first *aporia* addressed the question whether wisdom entails one science for the primary causes of being or several causes. If we again follow Menn’s interpretation of the final answer to the first *aporia* in *Metaphysics* Λ.10, we also find Aristotle using the results of his response to address the ways his predecessors failed. For instance, Anaxagoras is correct to posit the good, i.e. intellect (νοῦς), as the efficient cause for all things, yet errs by implicitly attributing the final cause to some other factor distinct from the good. This misses a crucial feature about the good itself, especially as divine thought or intellect (νοῦς): the final cause is one and the same with the efficient cause in the case of the good.¹⁴⁸ This follows on Aristotle’s argument in *Metaphysics* Λ.7 that the unmoved mover, as divine self-thinking intellect, moves all things as a final cause. As we saw in Menn’s reading, the identification of the final and efficient cause in the first, unmoved mover is what enables a final answer to the first *aporia*’s puzzle of wisdom

¹⁴⁶ E.g. Damascius, *DPI*, 96,1–2: “For the determined concept concerns a reality [or ‘thing’] which is determined”. (ἡ γὰρ διωρισμένη ἔννοια τοῦ διωρισμένου ἐστὶ πράγματος.)

¹⁴⁷ This becomes reflected across the scale of principles: (1) the Ineffable transcends all conception (e.g. *DPI*, 7,18–8,5), speech, opinion (as ἀδόξαστον: see *DP I*, 14,20–16,17), even to the point of περιτροπή, overturning in speech and thought; (2) the One admits of speech, but only by negation (ἀπόφασις)—hence no concept properly pertains to the One in itself (e.g. *DP I*, 94,13–18); finally (3) at the level of the intelligible (or “unified”), to the degree it is thought, determinate concepts apply to it, though in itself, apart from being thought and considered in its unity, distinct concepts do not apply to it. (See e.g. *DP III*, 135,13–136,21, with Damascius’ claim that the intelligible triad (or in the literal proposition, “what is common of the three principles/entities”) should be counted “as a whole” rather than distinctly or separately; as he illustrates in his pithy locution in 136,8–9: “Speaking generally, we should not count the intelligible on our fingers” (ὅλως δὲ φάναι, μὴ ἐπὶ δακτύλων ἀριθμῶμεν τὸ νοητόν). On this in connection to Damascius’ framework of the intelligible triad in relation to the *Philebus*’ Limit–Unlimited–Mixture triad, see Van Riel (2002) and Greig (2021) 248–257, 265–269.) All this yet again mirrors Buddensiek’s claim above with Aristotle and how *aporiai* rise in the first place: cf. earlier n. 134.

¹⁴⁸ Aristotle, *Met.* Λ.10, 1075b8–10: “Anaxagoras makes the good a moving principle; for intellect (νοῦς) moves things, but moves them for the sake of something, which must be something other than it, except according to our way of stating the case; for the medical art is in a sense health” (trans. Ross, modified).

as one science oriented around four, distinct causes—or rather, as implied in *Metaphysics* Λ.10, two which are identical in one object.

Similarly in Damascius' case, if we look at *De Principiis* II, 1–39, we find the final resolution of the first *aporia* from *DP* I, 1–2, employed in Damascius' overview of his Platonist predecessors on the kind and number of first principles before the intelligible triad (i.e. Being, Life, and Intellect). In the beginning Damascius reviews three positions: (1) two first principles (implicitly the Ineffable and the One) before the triad, corresponding to Iamblichus;¹⁴⁹ (2) one first principle (the Ineffable identified with the One), corresponding to Proclus, as well as Syrianus and Theodore of Asine;¹⁵⁰ and (3) nothing prior to the triad—the first principle equated with the first term (Being/the intelligible) of the intelligible triad, corresponding to Porphyry.¹⁵¹ While quickly dismissing Porphyry's latter position for failing to affirm the principle's transcendence and universality, Damascius critiques Proclus' identification of the One and Ineffable in one principle, since it ultimately makes the principle contradistinguished with its contrary, i.e. plurality—like the juxtaposition of the *Philebus*' two principles of Limit and Unlimited.¹⁵² This roughly mirrors the problem intuited in the first *aporia*'s Horn (A*), where the principle—despite initially claimed as “before” all things—becomes related to that which comes after it. For Damascius, distinguishing the Ineffable apart from the One guarantees the transcendent status of the first principle.

With this in mind, Iamblichus' position on the number of principles is correct for Damascius, and comes close to the position he advocates—though with important caveats. Among several *aporiai* raised on Iamblichus' position,¹⁵³ one is that Iamblichus ascribes mutually exclusive contrariety to the One (or One-All/Limit) and its corresponding principle of plurality (or All-One/Unlimited). However such opposition belongs to the domain of “all things” (τὰ πάντα), over which the One-All and All-One are principles. Opposition cannot be ascribed to the two principles, since they exist in pure unity, and are consequently without the distinction characteristic of opposition.¹⁵⁴ We see, again, the problem of concepts (ἐννοιαί) implying distinction imported and applied to the principles in Iamblichus' position. Damascius' response to Iamblichus comes about as the result of his attempt in *De Principiis* I to balance describing the One and the emergence of plurality from it with the ontological state of unity that predominates in the One's domain—denying any language or concepts straightforwardly implying distinction.¹⁵⁵ One can then see how the first *aporia* and its two horns stimulate this investigation: just as the resulting impasse demonstrated the need to re-clarify the concepts by which the soul may still grasp the absolute principle (i.e. the Ineffable) beyond duality, so it also made clear the need to re-

¹⁴⁹ Damascius, *DP* II, 2,11–16,19.

¹⁵⁰ Damascius, *DP* II, 16,20–39,27.

¹⁵¹ Damascius, *DP* II, 2,1–10.

¹⁵² Damascius, *DP* II, 21,1–22,10.

¹⁵³ Damascius reviews four arguments from Iamblichus in *DP* II, 3,3–6,15 and then sets up critical, opposing arguments to each of these in 6,16–14,21.

¹⁵⁴ See the fourth argument for Iamblichus in Damascius, *DP* II, 5,8–6,15, and the *aporia* raised on it in 7,1–11,25 (esp. 7,7–8,11). Cf. *DP* II, 15,12–20.

¹⁵⁵ Cf. above, n. 119.

orient the One's relation to all things (τὰ πάντα) as their “summit”, namely as *also* beyond duality, but also as the starting point and cause of the duality characteristic in τὰ πάντα.

Hence, Damascius parallels Aristotle's strategy of resolving *aporiai* by reassessing their dialectical premises—either in themselves or in relation to the positions of other philosophical predecessors. In Aristotle's case, *Metaphysics* B's first *aporia* becomes resolved by a reconsideration of the meaning of the “primary causes” toward which wisdom is oriented—which, on Menn's reading, corresponds to the “good” itself, which in turn allows for Aristotle's responses to the incomplete premises of Anaxagoras and other predecessors. In the same way in Damascius' case, the *De Principiis*' first *aporia* becomes resolved by a reconsideration of the term, “all things” (τὰ πάντα), and the way in which “principle” as a term of priority stands in relation to it. In both cases, as discussed above, the kind of resolution we see does not mean a refutation of one or the other horn in the *aporia*, nor a simple acceptance of one or the other thesis critiqued: instead the resolution goes beyond the initial *aporia*, preserving the initial impasse, and in fact depending on the premises in both contradictory sets to arrive at a resolution beyond them.¹⁵⁶ Damascius' reassessment leads to a two-fold distinction in “principle”, corresponding to the One (as the first, manifest cause of all things) and the Ineffable (as the first, uncoordinated (ἀσύνητακτον) principle of all things), which in turn allows him to assess and respond to the incomplete premises of Iamblichus' and Proclus' positions. An important key in this reassessment is an evaluation of what is implied in dialectical premises, as we saw above, and how they lead to the opposing positions characteristic of *aporiai*. In the case of the first *aporia*, Damascius exploits this aspect of opposition between terms as mirroring the opposition characteristic of “all things” in themselves: this becomes crucial for being able to discuss the Ineffable and the One, as both existing beyond the characteristic duality of “all things”, albeit in distinct ways.

Conclusion

Overall we have looked at elements of Aristotle's reception in Damascius' *De Principiis* with the aporetic method and use of dialectical premises. *Metaphysics* B in this regard presents a parallel to the *De Principiis*, inasmuch as Aristotle in the former uses the *aporiai* to establish the agenda for the rest of the *Metaphysics*, much in the same way the *De Principiis* utilizes its *aporiai* to establish the agenda of investigating the Platonist principles of beings. We briefly investigated this parallel in Section 1, while in Section 2 we discussed the background of Aristotle's aporetic method in the preface of *Metaphysics* B. An important qualifier we saw in Aristotle's methodological preface in B.1 is that certain kinds of *aporiai* involve resolutions which do not imply a refutation of one or the other thesis or horn, but rather a dialectical argument that preserves the initial *aporia*, with the resolution as beyond it—a case we see applied especially in the first *aporiai* of both Aristotle and Damascius. In Section 3 we compared the *De Principiis*' first *aporia* with *Metaphysics* B's first *aporia*: both are effectively the main, overriding questions with which both the *Metaphysics* and *De Principiis* are respectively concerned, where in Aristotle's case, the unity of the science of wisdom is at stake, while in Damascius' case, the relation and notion of the first principle in relation to all things (τὰ πάντα) is at stake. How both resolve their *aporiai* in markedly similar ways demonstrates a certain parallel in their intention of using the aporetic method: namely to

¹⁵⁶ Cf. above, n. 49.

elucidate a proper way to speak about the principles of beings, or all things, aimed at their reality to the closest degree possible. Of course one clear difference between the two is that Damascius' *aporia* indicates a subjective issue with an inherent limitation of thought—i.e. in thinking of a principle beyond all duality—whereas Aristotle's *aporia* is more concerned with an objective, external problem—i.e. how the kinds of causes correspond to one (or many) science. Yet, as discussed above, Damascius' subjective issue indicates an objective issue in relating the levels of reality, between the realm of duality and unity—and what lies beyond unity. It is in this specific respect that we find Damascius' approach correlating with Aristotle's.

Hence, the comparison of Damascius' method with Aristotle's in *Metaphysics* B shows how Damascius' treatise is a kind of return to Aristotle's way of conducting the inquiry into metaphysics in a dialectical manner: this involves thoroughly reviewing the positions of past predecessors and beginning anew by raising difficulties and, in so doing, finding new ways to proceed in the inquiry into the principles in themselves. Despite the objective focus in Aristotle's case, one finds Aristotle's methodology building on the Platonic background of dialogues like the *Meno*, where the aporetic state is essential to be able to inquire into the principles of reality. As a committed Platonist, Damascius works much within this frame, albeit to a distinct, radical degree, yet here we see him incorporating aspects of Aristotle within a common Platonic frame of *aporia* as the guiding principle of conducting metaphysics. The distinct contribution of Damascius is that he ties the dialectical method more strongly to our level of reality: understanding the principles of being in themselves, which transcend us, means finding a way to manifest on our level what cannot be manifested on the principles' level.

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⁵⁷ Abbreviations for cited editions in brackets (where applicable). Full titles also in brackets, if not listed in title.

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